

Hidden REF 2021 submissions

More information at

<https://hidden-ref.org/hidden-ref-2021-competition/>

Hidden Role panel

Entry: 40

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role
Hidden role: Data stewards and managers
Role submitted: n/a
Name: Stevelink, Sharon
Organisation/University: N/A
Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A
Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

I would like to nominate David Pernet and Daniel Leightley who are heavily involved in data management and information governance in the Department of Psychological Medicine. David has been working hard to get our team afloat during the COVID-19 pandemic when everything had to be accessed remotely, including access to sensitive military data. Both David and Dan have been essential and instrumental in ensuring that the information governance and GDPR has been up to date over the last couple of years. Most of their effort and input happens behind the scenes but without that, we would not be able to continue to deliver our research.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A
Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A
Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 43

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: RMAs (Research Managers and Administrators)

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Freeman, Matthew

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Leila Whitworth Head of Research Strategy and Funding Team Medical Sciences Division Oxford University Leila Whitworth embodies the hidden REF. Leading a small team in Oxford University's Medical Sciences Division (MSD), and despite her name appearing rarely, she is the architect of much of Oxford's success in biomedical research funding and strategy. Her role is multi-faceted and complex, reflecting the scale of the MSD (5,600 staff and research income of over £350m/yr). Her contributions go far beyond drafting and overseeing complex proposals. She creates and spots opportunities; nurtures nascent academic vision into reality; builds strategy, governance, and ambition into projects; coaches PIs; and navigates political minefields. Even this understates the scale of her role. Fundamentally, she is responsible for shaping Oxford's world-class biomedical research and ambition into a structured set of strategic initiatives (e.g. new institutes, networks, interdisciplinary collaborations) that maximise our research power. She also leads processes like the REF, although one of Leila's essential abilities is cutting through, and shielding researchers from, bureaucracy. Leila has been a pilot of Oxford's widely acknowledged success in responding to COVID-19. In addition to guiding the avalanche of activity, Leila created an internal COVID-19 research fund. She managed the review of 256 applications, making 90 awards in 11 weeks. In setting up a streamlined but rigorous process, she maximised the impact of resources, while also focusing on the need for speed: saving time has literally saved lives. Finally, Leila works with calm, grace and sensitivity in what can be a febrile environment. A senior research manager by the age of 24, at 33 now, she is a linchpin in the tiny leadership team that steers UK's largest university biomedical research institution. Leila is also a generous mentor of others, as well as a role model and advocate for 'hidden' university roles.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 46

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Technicians

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Laycock, Elizabeth

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

I should like to nominate Carl James (technician at SHU) for his support of the research work undertaken in the Harmer labs at SHU for Natural and Built Environment. Carl has worked diligently to construct many items of bespoke laboratory test equipment, has been a mainstay of the technical team in the execution and support of the testing for the research. In addition to this he is well known and respected by the final year undergraduates for keeping an eye on them and ensuring that their project work is progressing well. He has had to juggle child care and working during Covid-19 which he has managed successfully, which is much to his credit. He is keen to continue to learn and develop his skills and is a very valued member of the Harmer team. I do not like to think of him as being undervalued and therefore want to ask that his contribution is considered as without him my research would be almost impossible to deliver, and more importantly the world would be a little sadder a place without his cheery input.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 51

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role
Hidden role: Professional Services Personnel
Role submitted: n/a
Name: Powis, Chris
Organisation/University: N/A
Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A
Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

I wish to nominate Dawn Hibbert, Head of Research Support based in Library and Learning Services (LLS) at the University of Northampton for her outstanding work in both supporting research and, more pertinently, at one point single-handedly driving our REF submission. Dawn's job description requires her to support research activity, principally through the management of the university repository and by contributing to training and support for researchers and their supervisors. She also has a role in facilitating and supporting the research activity of LLS. Over the past four years she has consistently acted over and above this, including acting as the main driving force behind our REF submission for a significant period before the appointment of a new Dean of Research in 2020. During this time she convinced University management to purchase PURE as our (first) Current Research Information System to sit alongside the eprints repository. This has proved essential for our REF submission, but previous post holders had never managed to get their business case accepted and Dawn pushed it on through sheer force of will. She also battled significant IT issues in making it operational while coordinating academics in collecting outputs, creating Impact Case Studies and working on the Environment Statement alongside her 'day job'. She also lobbied for and won administrative staff to boost her team and despite not having had much line management experience, created a small but high performing team. Throughout the REF process she has been brilliant at flattering, cajoling and supporting academic colleagues with their submission. She has also been clear and fair in those difficult conversations when research was not able to be submitted and her deep knowledge of the process and her excellent networks have enabled her to speak with authority to all levels of the University about the REF.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A
Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A
Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 52

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Technicians

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Ahmed, Jiteen

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

I would like to nominate Daniel Burrell, Hayley Smith and Rachel Heath for their vital contribution to supporting the research at Aston University. They have each contributed to ensure that key facilities continue to run safely and that equipment are regularly maintained. For example, Hayley has support the NMR facility, ensuring that Liquid Nitrogen and helium top ups are organised and undertaken. Hayley also ensures that there is full compliance with regulations related to the NMR facility as well. Hayley has also ensured that equipment in the Medicinal Chemistry Facility (which is funded by £4M of research funding) is maintained correctly, failure to do so would mean we would be delayed in meeting key deadlines, which with Hayley's support we have not missed. Daniel has been an asset to the Neuroscience facility by ensuring regular maintenance of equipment and supporting key research work in this area. for example, Daniel supported a project which had a tight deadline and needed to be delivered to the USA in time, without his knowledge and support, the deadline wouldn't have been met and further opportunities couldve been lost. Rachel has been a massive support for the Pharmaceuticals area in which she has helped support key advances in the field of Pharmaceuticals. Not only has Rachel supported the maintenance of equipment but she has gone out of her way to ensure projects can take place safely. Daniel, Hayley and Rachel have done a lot of work where their knowledge has helped further research and have always gone above and beyond what is expected of Technical staff and so it is my pleasure to nominate them for this award.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 56

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Technicians

Role submitted: n/a

Name: McGregor, Nicholas

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Sam Hart carries out many essential duties supporting our work-flows for sample mounting, freezing, testing and diffraction within the York Structural Biology Laboratory. As a researcher working to solve the structures of biological macromolecules, I depend on Sam's excellent maintenance of stocks of essential reusable equipment including clean and well-organized crystal mounting loops, dry tools for handling crystals, a readily available supply of liquid nitrogen, and well-organized safety equipment for handling cryogenic liquids. I also rely on Sam's expert maintenance and care of the X-ray diffraction equipment within YSBL and on his ability to reliably integrate crystals from across YSBL into a bespoke sample management system that significantly reduces the amount of time spent identifying high quality crystals suitable for sending to Diamond Light Source for diffraction. Lastly, Sam's pro-active management of data has consistently enabled the efficient determination of high quality molecular structures suitable for publication in top-tier journals and has prevented any data mishaps or archiving issues that commonly arise.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 57

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role
Hidden role: Professional Services Personnel
Role submitted: n/a
Name: Nicoll Baines, Katie
Organisation/University: N/A
Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A
Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

I am nominating Dr Sara Shinton, Head of Researcher Development at the University of Edinburgh and the wider Researcher Development team that she leads. Researcher Development at UoE provides a bedrock of support for all research staff and students. This takes the form of planning, sourcing and delivering training programmes that enable researchers to operate successfully, write papers and grants and develop their careers and management styles. They routinely consult heads of schools across the university to ensure a comprehensive understanding of researcher needs and requirements for development as well as working strategically with the University executive to implement the Researcher Development Concordat as well as other initiatives designed to recruit and retain research staff. A notable initiative that Sara and her team have been instrumental in is the recent internal recruitment of 40 Chancellor's Fellows at UoE. Sara was an integral part of the team responsible for the strategy and implementation of the recruitment process. She and Nicola Cuthbert are now leading on the coordination of training for the fellows that have been appointed and will be critical in supporting their development as a cohort. These initiatives are integral contributions towards the growth of research excellence at UoE. Additionally, Sara has been a key driving factor in pushing for an in-depth review of the recruitment process for these prestigious fellowships. She has supported the review design, ensuring access to all aspects of the process to facilitate a comprehensive understanding of what can be learned from the exercise with a view to making recommendations for future activities to support researcher development in the university. This work deserves recognition has part of the hidden REF because it forms such an integral part of the research excellence at the University of Edinburgh.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A
Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A
Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 59

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Technicians

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Ferguson, Michael

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Douglas Lamont is Manager of our extensive proteomics facility of 17 mass spectrometry systems, sample preparation hardware, data analysis software and a technician/post-doctoral staff of 6. Doug has managed the facility for more than 20 years and it is the lifeblood of our previous (and hopefully next) REF success. The majority of our REF publication outputs and impact case studies are based upon the superb ultra-high technology platforms that he provides to the Schools of Life Sciences and Medicine in Dundee. Indeed, Doug also provides these services to numerous UK and international universities, research institutes and companies. Recent examples of his outstanding initiative include: Keeping our proteomics facility fully functional throughout all of the pandemic, not least to support vital COVID-19 research involving our Schools of Life Sciences and Medicine. All of this was skillfully done without compromising the health and wellbeing of his staff. On his own initiative, he secured £170k by selling off de-commissioned instruments. This satisfied our desire for sustainability by providing the machines with a second life and our need to invest in the latest generation of mass spectrometry technology, in this case a package of new Thermo Eclipse and Exploris instruments and a post-doc to develop new methodologies. In particular, this will support cutting edge research into T-cell biology and into tropical diseases such as malaria and leishmaniasis to improve the lives of millions. The latter avenue of research formed the basis of three of our impact case studies in our recent REF submission. We wish to publicise Dougie's superb abilities, dedication and initiative widely so that he gets the recognition that we believe he deserves as one of our unsung heroes, and to make others in the sector aware of the significance of the possibilities of equipment resale to the furtherance of research.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 61

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Community Manager

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Botchway, Stan

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Successful proposal to national facilities needs to be recognised better in REF. at the cost of >£8k per week, this is an excellent additional source of funding to the researcher.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 62

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Technicians

Role submitted: n/a

Name: strachan, gregory

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Greg Strachan is a technician in the Institute of Metabolic Science (IMS) in Cambridge, a world-leading research institute devoted to metabolic disease. Through dynamism and technical ability allied to excellent interpersonal skills, Greg has transformed many aspects of how the IMS operates. One of his key roles is to run our Core Imaging Facility. Through appropriate courses he trained himself as a microscopist and is now highly adept in a broad range of microscopic techniques and a much valued trainer of students and post docs. It was Greg's initiative that resulted in the acquisition of Halo software, which employs innovative artificial intelligence algorithms to enable tissue specification in histological preparations. He also pushed for the acquisition of the Opera Phenix high-content platform rather than a simple replacement of an old confocal microscope, increasing the capability of the core. In annual surveys of internal and external users the praise for the quality of service that Greg provides is a recurring theme. In his general role in the department Greg is constantly seeking to improve processes to increase efficiency and facilitate research. He led the project to identify and install the best wireless monitoring and reporting system for all crucial freezers in the Institute, replacing an outdated system. He implemented a centralised IT booking and monitoring system for all our Core Facilities, Tissue Culture and equipment which has had a hugely positive impact on research operations. Greg's commitment to the IMS shone through during COVID where he was one of two core staff who were physically present throughout all phases of lockdown. He set up a QR system for recording staff entry and exit which was crucial for facilitating reopening in the early summer of 2020. It would be wonderful to see his sustained "above and beyond" contributions recognised by this award

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 64

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Other

Role submitted: postdoc

Name: Ottersbach, Katrin

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

I would like to nominate my postdoc Camille Malouf, who has really become my second in command, fulfilling the role of a successful postdoc who is now in the process of establishing herself as an independent researcher with her own lab, as well as being a lab manager. She has not only driven her own research in my lab completely independently, resulting in 5 first author publications, with another in revision and another in preparation, but has made other major contributions to the lab, including keeping the research going and looking after our mouse models during the first lockdown, keeping the lab stocked and equipment working, representing me on several committees, looking after precious human samples, taking part in public engagement activities and working tirelessly with limitless enthusiasm, completely committed. She is a fountain of knowledge and has produced a massive amount of high quality data that the lab will benefit from for years to come. At the time she joined my lab in 2012, we started on two new lines of research: the developmental origins of infant leukaemia and the involvement of miRNAs, both of which she drove forward almost single-handedly. As my lab moved from Cambridge to Edinburgh, she took on many responsibilities during the move, even bringing up lab equipment and reagents in a van and re-establishing the lab, techniques and mouse colonies. She is the centre of the lab, knowing where everything is and how everything is done. She has also established a number of new and essential technologies in the lab, such as viral transductions, intra-femoral injections, xenotransplants and standardised protocols for flow cytometry and for the analysis of leukaemia mouse models. It will be an immense loss when she leaves, but I wish her all the best for her own, independent career.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 71

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: RMAs (Research Managers and Administrators)

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Fovargue, Sara

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Nominating Gill Harrison, Impact Director, Lancaster University. Gill has provided exceptional support to Impact Leads and ICS authors at the Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences at Lancaster University. She was an incredible source of knowledge, wisdom, and experience, and has supported all departmental REF and Impact leads through some sensitive matters within the School and across Faculties. Gill is a consummate professional, and is patient, kind, and thoughtful with an excellent sense of humour, which is particularly important when delivering 'unwanted' news. Gill has consistently gone over and above what could reasonably be expected of her, often at great personal cost to herself and her family. This nomination comes with endorsement from a number of REF leads and ICS authors; Jonathan Culpepper (Linguistics): 'The "Gill factor" has enabled not only our REF ICS but also our environment statement to improve immeasurably. Gill has worked tirelessly – well beyond the call of duty – not just advising us, but scrutinising drafts with her laser-like eye and suggesting improvements, big and small. We are deeply indebted to her'. Rachel Cooper, (LICA): 'Gill has worked tirelessly, including many weekends, and she makes light work for academics. Her work has been exceptional and her support amazing'. Elena Semino, (Linguistics): 'Gill is a huge asset to the FASS REF team. I have been consistently impressed by her depth of understanding of REF requirements, the sharpness of her criticisms of drafts of submissions, and the quality of her suggestions and revisions. She is, by a long way, the person whose judgement I value (and fear!) the most as a reviewer of the ICS I lead. Nobody else's input has made nearly as much difference to the final version as Gill's, and she will deserve a big part of the credit for any success we have"

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 72

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role
Hidden role: Other
Role submitted: PostDoctoral Researcher
Name: Costa Gomes, Beatriz
Organisation/University: N/A
Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A
Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Dr. Andre Voelzmann is an imperative presence in our research lab, at the University of Manchester. Over the last five years, Andre has been the backbone of all projects and collaborations, as well as an incredible communicator and manager. While not officially, Andre has taken a supervisory role in my project. Doing all of the drosophila maintenance and cell culture experiments, as well as imaging, Andre's work was pivotal in my entire thesis, where I analyse the images he produced. Given his knowledge of computational sciences too, he guided me on my project when neither of my supervisors could. Andre is a very dutiful, responsible and perseverant scientist, working through tirelessly to not only accomplish his work but actually to help everyone around him, from students, to technicians and other postdocs or fellows. In fact, he pushes himself so much to help everyone around that he ends up neglecting his own career needs. This is the reason why I want to nominate him: he is a selfless person that falls behind in the normal via of academia as he wants to help others more than himself. His work has helped and shaped at least three PhD projects, and guided so many other smaller endeavours. Andre has the patience and takes the time to learn, listen, and educate. In fact, his presence is so important that we, the students, nominated him for outstanding postdoc at the Faculty, which he won. In short, Andre is a rare mixture of kindness and intelligence, that make him a powerful yet silent scientist in a world full of loud voices.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A
Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A
Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 73

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Community Manager

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Pickard-Smith, Kelly

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

I am one of the Directors and Founders of Women in Academia Support Network (WIASN). WIASN is a global social network representing over 100 countries and 11k+ members from PhD to Vice Chancellor. A model of peer social digital learning managed by community managers and moderators (I even took a Facebook qualification in Community Management!). Four years old, WIASN recently gained charitable status. The beauty of the network is the flattening of hierarchy where all members equally contribute and a 24-7 support space. I have most recently curated member content to form over 14 learning guides containing more than 150 resources to support academic career, including writing, publishing and impact support and of course REF. However, WIASN is very cognizant that it takes a village to produce research and also push for acceptance of practice/arts based and 'alternative' forms of knowing and producing impactful research – and the power and privilege behind who can produce, who is credited and what counts as impactful research. As well as the resources we also have a spin off writing group, we've held writing retreats, partnered with Focusmate App to partner for virtual working and Emerald Global Publishing to support members. The best feeling is seeing members support each other through celebration and strife. Recent REF necessitated a lot of cat Gifs and funny memes to get them through it. REF submission was a difficult, emotional, often isolating and exhausting time for many but the membership pulled together– highlighting the oft neglected emotional and social needs of REF – it takes a toll! When we see the acknowledgements in members books, arts/practice based outputs, thesis and journal articles dedicated to WIASN, the membership and the support they gained from it we realize just how important community is.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 78

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role
Hidden role: Research Software Engineers
Role submitted: n/a
Name: Lewis, Rodney
Organisation/University: N/A
Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A
Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

I nominate Rodney Lewis and the NaN team at the IoPPN for amazing and dedicated support of the NaN servers and HPC system, providing invaluable assistance to researchers and students. Never a question too stupid, or a request too difficult to consider. So many papers at the IoPPN will have never been published without their invaluable support. My lab is certainly in debt to them, and I know for sure that so many do as well.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A
Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A
Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 79

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: RMAs (Research Managers and Administrators)

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Gadd, Elizabeth

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

I'd like to submit all UK research managers and administrators into the Hidden REF, and especially those who contribute to the ongoing conversation about the REF itself in an effort to improve it. These professionals experience daily and first-hand the impact of the REF on their academic colleagues, and the UK research system as a whole. As such they are constantly bringing critical and experienced perspectives to questions around what the REF is for, who it should reward, and what it should look like. These are the ambassadorial people who seek to represent the views of academia to assessors, and the views of assessors to academia, all with the aim of ultimately navigating towards a negotiated better future. There are a lot of voices in this space but I would particularly highlight those of Kirsty Allen, Julie Bayley, Anna Grey, Kieran Fenby-Hulse, and Hilary Noone.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 85

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Lived Experience Contributors

Role submitted: n/a

Name: van Blerk, Lorraine

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Eighteen street children and youth made a unique and outstanding contribution as lived experience contributors to research through the Growing Up on the Streets Project. For three years (2012/3-2016), they worked as street researchers, engaging in ethnographic observations and reporting in the African cities of Accra (Ghana), Bukavu (DRC), and Harare (Zimbabwe). Their weekly narrative accounts document the lived experience of 229 young people growing up on the streets in their communities and networks. They also led their networks of street peers in ten quarterly focus group discussions around their 'capabilities', which many of them helped to define in a pilot stage. Following this data collection period, the young researchers continued to work with Growing up on the Streets as activists on the streets, fighting for the rights of children and youth living in street situations; assisting with data analysis, creating dissemination tools and outputs, engaging with stakeholders and governments through knowledge exchange workshops (in some cases internationally); as well as active street work in their cities. Some of this group continue as street champions supporting local NGOs in their work even today. During the entire process, all of the young people lived on the streets and worked tirelessly to support their friends, despite personal hardships. Through undertaking this research their voices were part of the consultation process (in further focus groups across the three cities) for the UN General Comment 21 (2017) on the rights of children in street situations. The outcome of their contributions to research directly fed into Research Excellence Framework publications and an impact case study. Outputs they were directly involved in include an award-winning training pack (2016), two story maps (2017, 2020) and briefing papers (2012-2018). They deserve recognition for their role in this project.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 86

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role
Hidden role: Data stewards and managers
Role submitted: n/a
Name: Mowat, Mary
Organisation/University: N/A
Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A
Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

I am a data manager at the British Geological Survey working on various projects across disciplines. I make a large contribution to national and international high impact research resulting in countless publications though this contribution is not currently well recognised and I'm not named on publications. Through ESO (ECORD Science Operator), the European operator for IODP (International Ocean Discovery Programme), I coordinate IT infrastructure and data management for various expeditions (such as Expedition 364 Chicxulub Impact Crater) to explore the earth under the sea. I participate during both offshore (on Mission Specific Platforms) and onshore phases. A huge number of datasets and high impact publications by the international science party members result from this data which I have helped them collect to very high IODP standards. My work will also enable many future publications from the openly available data, https://iodp.pangaea.de/front_content.php?idcat=112. UK Geoenergy Observatories is a large infrastructure project related to clean energy such as geothermal. I work with the researchers to ensure they publish their data openly in an exemplar way, <https://www.ukgeos.ac.uk/data-downloads>. I have contributed to a large number of publications and net-zero aims, <https://www.ukgeos.ac.uk/data/publications>. In SECURE (Subsurface Evaluation of CCS and Unconventional Risks), an EU Horizon 2020 project, I work with project partners across Europe to maximise access to, and future re-use of data they generate contributing to a large number of publications. <https://www.securegeoenergy.eu/data-resources>, <https://www.securegeoenergy.eu/publications>. I run the MEDIN Data Archive Centre for Marine Geology and Geophysics, improving access to seabed and sub-seabed data and making data available for the whole UK marine and coastal community including researchers, <https://www.bgs.ac.uk/geological-data/national-geoscience-data-centre/ngdc-data-management/marine-geoscience-data-management/>. I run the UKCSSRC Data and Information Archive on behalf of UKCSSRC and work with researchers from various universities to publish their data. This improves knowledge exchange and speeds up innovation in the field of Carbon Capture and Storage, <https://www2.bgs.ac.uk/ukccs/>.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A
Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A
Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 93

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: PRISMS (Professional Research Investment and Strategy Managers)

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Hibbins, Alastair

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Dr Anja Roeding is pivotal to the success to our Research Centre and the UK Metamaterials community. Employed as programme manager of the CDT in Metamaterials in 2017, she has since taken on an increasing amount of responsibility and received growing recognition as she builds local, national and international connections. She has grown effectively into the Operations Lead for Metamaterials at Exeter and the UK Metamaterials Network. Her key competencies are people, communication, and coordination. Her active listening skills and empathy builds trusting relationships with PGRs, PDRs, academics, and external partners, and facilitates links to develop new ideas and provide career opportunities. Her analytical thinking turned this into the development of a nation-wide metamaterials expert database that feeds into strategic documents like the EPSRC Big Idea “Metamaterials Revolution” to drive this research area for the benefit of the UK. Anja links academics to industry and Government partners across the UK and internationally, in order to drive impact and collaborations. She mentors PhD students in our centre who wish to proceed with a career outside of academia. Dr Roeding facilitates, and drives the work of academics, making their efforts more efficient and impactful, while performing a leadership role, e.g. by developing a PGR/industry mentoring programme to coordination of professional services; chairing national leadership team meetings; co-developing proposals (e.g. large-scale collaborations and investments like EPSRC CDT, Network, Centre-to-Centre, Big Idea); building websites and managing our external profile. In 2020/21, she was invited speaker at VITAE on “strategic research management”, at a SORSE event on Building and Managing a Professional Community, and at an Innovate UK/KTN event to introduce the EPSRC UK Metamaterials Network. Anja's breadth is her strength: It is the invisible yet invaluable glue that closes gaps, creates new links and opportunities, and is simply not recognised via the usual HEI metrics.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 94

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Other

Role submitted: Volunteers (organisers, mentors, experts, maintainers and participants)

Name: Yehudi, Yo

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Open Life Science (OLS, <https://openlifesci.org/>) broadens access to structured training and mentoring in open science. Through 16-week cohort-based programmes, we support individuals and potential academic leaders in applying research best practices in their work and becoming open science ambassadors in their communities. Participants receive training by experts, mentoring by open science practitioners, and community platforms for peer-learning with cohort members. Since 2020, we have trained 146 participants from 6 continents across 45 low- and middle- (LMICs), and high-income countries (HICs). The OLS curriculum purposefully guides our diverse members to reflect on and integrate open, inclusive and collaborative practices in the context of their socio-economic condition, where they conduct their research. The value we create in OLS is impossible without the hard work of our volunteers who participate in the programme beyond their day job. We are committed to highlighting and recognising their hidden roles in OLS as organisers, mentors, experts, maintainers and participants, and as volunteers within the broader open science ecosystems. Our training and mentoring formats are intentionally designed to be inclusive of our participants' accessibility needs and we support projects with both technical and non-technical scopes (reference: <https://osf.io/k3bfn/>). To further support their engagement, we create opportunities for skill-building through informal discussions and technical workshops. Moreover, we create pathways for our graduates to take on leadership roles beyond OLS. Starting this year, we allocated community support fund raised through grants and delivering ally-skills workshops. We offered honoraria to our mentors and microgrants to our participants, especially for those in LMICs. These efforts have led to building a mutually supportive community of practice with over 250 members (<https://openlifesci.org/community>). They empower each other to lead and contribute to the community-oriented development of research tools, practices and projects, educating researchers worldwide on the hands-on benefits of open science.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 95

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Technicians

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Fitch, Paul

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Shonna Johnston (Manager), Will Ramsay (Specialist) and Mari George (Assistant) The QMRI (Queens Medical Research Institute) Flow Cytometry and Cell Sorting Facility at the University of Edinburgh is staffed by a dynamic team of 3 technologists. The facility functions as an autonomous unit hosted by the Centre for Inflammation Research (CIR). Inflammatory disorders are amongst the major killers in the UK and uncontrolled can lead to scarring and organ dysfunction. Flow cytometry is a well-established method for identifying inflammatory cells. The facility staff support research by ensuring the state-of-the-art instruments are maintained to a high standard with emphasis on tracking instrument performance to ensure quality data and reproducibility; while promoting MIFlowCyt reporting standards. The team provide specialist expertise and are responsible for developing training and supporting researchers in all aspects of flow cytometry from sample preparation, panel design, sample acquisition, to data analysis and interpretation. This teaching extends to undergraduate learning via practical tutorials and data analysis training. Nationally, they are approached by other institutions for professional advice and are able to secure commercial contracts for assay development. They are adept at validating and implementing new techniques, anticipating changing demands and seizing opportunities to network and advance themselves and the facility to the benefit of the research output eg improved sustainability, public engagement involvement and the Technician's Commitment. More recently, the team was key in supporting the College COVID research by ensuring relevant health and safety documentation was prepared and adapting procedures to allow clinical trials to progress smoothly. I would like to nominate these technologists, as a team, as their achievements are based in their support each other and their willingness to exceed expectations. They provide a friendly and supportive research environment, and are integral to the vast majority of successful publications and grant applications that come from CIR.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 96

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Research Software Engineers

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Weinzierl, Marion

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

I would like to nominate Alison Clarke, who is a brilliant RSE. With more than 15 years of software engineering experience in industry she joined the Advanced Research Computing RSE team in Durham about 1.5 years ago. She has worked with researchers from a range of departments - Psychology, Music, Physics, Education, to name a few - and not only helped in her field of expertise, which is web and application development, but also expanded her own expertise to other fields, such as agent-based simulations. Her work has made (and continues to make) new research possible. She also was one of the leading people to build up our multi- and cross-disciplinary Research Methods Conversations at Durham, and build an amazing system to coordinate and plan the RSE work in our team. She has served in the programme committee of the international Series of Online Research Software Events (SORSE) over the past year, and has now become a Fellow of the Software Sustainability Institute, aiming to develop domain-specific approaches to provide RSE support. Although she still doubts whether, without a PhD, she is right in the PhD-dominated field of RSE, she is a role model and someone to look up to when it comes to being an RSE, supporting researchers, and reaching out to non-traditional fields to expand our collaboration to.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 97

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Librarians

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Weightman, Alison

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Members of Cardiff University Library's Open Research Team provide perfect examples of largely unsung but fundamental roles in the REF submission. These include: • The Institutional Repository Team who checked the individual details of 6,256 records for accuracy and compliance with the REF criteria and – in the last year alone – liaised with researchers to increase the number of open access publications in the Repository by 5,606; • The Library REF Manager who worked closely with the University's REF Operations Group to provide advice and support on outputs, impact and environment statements – going so far to adapt her spare room into a print copy repository prior to submission to Research England!; • The Open Access, Research Data and Cardiff University's Diamond OA Press team who have contributed so much to the University's open research credentials within the Environment statements which celebrate 30,000 open research outputs and 3 million downloads per annum; • Finally, the research analytics specialist who cross-checked submissions against Web of Science records. The level of skills, that needed to be employed and shared with others involved in the submission, included in-depth system knowledge of the University repository (e-prints), its Current Research Information System (Converis), JISC Core, Unpaywall and Cross REF, and exceptional interpersonal skills for liaison with the large number of contributing colleagues across University academic schools and professional services. These contributions have been recognised by the University's Research Dean who reported that the University REF Manager "...highlighted the outstanding proactive contributions you are providing for us on REF". A sentiment echoed in the Vice Chancellor's message to the University, following the REF submission in March. In wanting "...to recognise the incredible team effort that has been made across the University" he made explicit reference to the crucial, albeit hidden, roles within the Library's Open Research Team.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 98

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Community Manager

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Karoune, Emma

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Malvika Sharan, The Turing Way Community Manager. The Turing Way is an open-source project that involves and supports its diverse community to make data science reproducible, ethical, collaborative and inclusive for everyone. As a community we are working to produce a resource, in the form of an online book, that makes reproducible research 'too easy not to do'. Malvika is at the forefront of the community demonstrating exceptional skills in community building. She achieves this through maintaining multiple channels of communication, documenting and maintaining the project through the open-source Github repository, and organising and running regular events such as co-working, collaboration cafes and onboarding sessions to support and bring in new members. She regularly gives talks to promote The Turing Way and leads in best practice for Reproducible Research (see this talk <https://zenodo.org/record/4633118#.YJUElrX0mUk>). The Turing Way is a global community consisting of members from diverse scientific disciplines. There is an extensive community handbook and onboarding procedure to enable mentored contributions. The resources in the book have grown to over 140 subchapters in 2 years by over 250 contributors. The impact of this resource is still growing but is reflected in the more than 4000 downloads from Zenodo. Over time the number of people sharing the project with their communities has grown, building a diverse set of voices that represent The Turing Way. Almost all of those voices build on Malvika's carefully curated slides and other resources as we scale this valuable, free, open source training resource. All this work is conducted in an inclusive and collaborative manner that sets apart The Turing Way as a positive force for changing research culture. We - the contributors to the project - would not be able to bring our best efforts to the community without Malvika's care, support, vision and leadership.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 101

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Technicians

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Mieszkowska, Nova

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Kevin Atkins has worked at the Marine Biological Association for thirty years. He is the MBA lab's marine engineer, however, this job title falls remarkably short of encapsulating the role that Kevin plays here. Kevin has unrivalled expertise in designing, constructing, maintaining, running, troubleshooting, and renovating the MBA's unique seawater system, complete with direct seawater supply from Plymouth Sound, four reservoirs with a 60,000 total volume, and a vast array of tank systems including one of the largest multiple stressor mesocosm systems in the UK, supporting published research-papers. He recently dismantled, removed, brought in a new system in parts, and reconstructed the entire seawater pumping system that runs from Plymouth Sound to the pump house, through two pumps, up to the MBA laboratory, into the reservoirs, around the entire laboratory tank system, and back down to the sea. This was a colossal job that he completed singlehandedly, and without most people in the laboratory even knowing that he had carried this out. Kevin's engineering, plumbing, electrical, and construction skills are constantly in demand both in the seawater hall and across the entire laboratory building. He designs and constructs marine sampling equipment, fixes laboratory kit, helps out on fieldwork when his skills are required to set up field experiments, and even fixes the kitchen sink – literally, when there are problems with the catering facilities. Kevin always goes above and beyond the call of duty. He works weekends, early mornings, and is on call to respond to any out of hours emergency that arises at the laboratory. His eternally positive, cheerful demeanor makes him a pleasure to work with, and he hides his voluminous light under a bushel, so that most of the time people don't realise what essential work he has carried out on a daily basis to keep the laboratory running smoothly.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 102

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: RMAs (Research Managers and Administrators)

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Wall, Natalie

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Dr Reetika Suri is an exemplary member of staff at Queen Mary University of London, known to colleagues for her loyalty and dedication to providing excellent service within her role, while always acting with the ambition of exceeding it. Reetika returned early from maternity leave and took on additional work in priority areas, in response to urgent issues arising in her absence. This past academic year and despite REF, Reetika created a team training strategy, developing 13 workshops. The Impact Team has trained twice as many staff and students as in the 2019/20 academic year. Reetika also led on the creation of the London Impact Support & Engagement Network (LISEN) in collaboration with UCL in May 2020. LISEN brings together a group of impact professionals across London to transfer skills by sharing practice. The network has hosted four online events and has a membership of over 40 impact professionals. Deputy Dean for Research Impact (DDRI), Faculty of Science and Engineering: "I have joined the faculty over a year ago and was immediately impressed by the engagement of Dr. Suri. [...] The result of Dr. Suri's collaborative work is a very strong submission for the upcoming REF of our Faculty. It is essential to note that along the course of the REF preparation process, Dr. Suri was given a significant additional workload, due to the departure of one of the Impact team member." DDRI, School of Medicine and Dentistry: "Reetika has been an invaluable part of the SMD REF 2021 Impact Team. Her steadfast work over the past years nurturing our Impact Cases from scratch has borne fruit this year in an excellent submission. I am in no doubt that any future success SMD has with regard to REF 2021 Impact will be in no small way down to Reetika's hard work."

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 112

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Librarians

Role submitted: n/a

Name: McLaren, Lisa

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Sam came into the role with no experience of REF with a year to submission. Around the same time, his baby was born 10 weeks early. And yet throughout, he was cheerful in the face of a barrage of questions, offered practical solutions to practice based research submissions and read up on everything, so he became an authoritative source of knowledge. We developed a significant problem with our repository 5 months before submission, which took 4 solid months of developing fixes with their team to get the REF2 data into good shape and in the end, we didn't submit a single technical exception. He'd previously worked in a Systems department and he was the only member of the team who could have undertaken the rigorous testing we needed, identified the flaws in the coding and translated all this to the developers. And all the while, trying to maintain the other aspects of his job, such as research finance and working with our CRIS, on top of the REF submission. He was also new to staff management and suddenly had to manage a team with some very big responsibilities through a major project, which he did with aplomb. He was motivating when he needed to be, he listened when the staff were having problems, both in and out of work, and he provided a much needed sense of calm and fun when we were in the run-up and times were tough. The university also underwent a number of changes at Research PVC level during the REF, but especially in the last 2 years and the senior member of staff in the library (myself) had not run a REF submission previously, so there was often a gap in planning and communications that Sam filled very well and I think without him, we'd have struggled to submit.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 113

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Technicians

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Rusbridge, Tom

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

In his 25-year career at King's College London, Stephen Franey has become widely admired by colleagues at the highest senior level and junior alike, across faculties, institutions, and job roles. Now the Technical Staff Development Manager, Stephen has been the champion at King's to recognise, develop and increase the visibility of technical staff. He has driven efforts to ensure that the university community fully understands and values the indispensable contributions of this group of staff who support our world-leading research. Collaborative, well-connected, and generous, Stephen co-leads the Technical Services Network, including promoting the network internally, chairing meetings, and running innovative away days that bring in senior sponsors, a range of speakers from across King's and external guests. Alongside other colleagues he set up an Apprenticeship Scheme, while individually he is the London and South East Network Coordinator for HEaTED, and mentors colleagues to undertake professional registration as the King's lead contact for the Science Council. He also successfully lobbied King's leadership to fund technical staff to undertake registration and provided extensive support to the Crick to help the first Crick cohort of technical staff submit their applications, generously sharing his course materials. This enabled the Crick to become Employer Champions, recognising their support for staff to undertake registration. Stephen was the driver to ensure that King's was a founding signatory of the Technician Commitment: a pledge to support our technicians to help address key challenges of recognition, progression and sustainability facing technical staff working in research. He was also instrumental in setting up a London-wide Technician Commitment signatories' group for Commitment Leads to meet and share ideas and best practice. Now leading on an initiative for Kings to become a training provider for L3 Laboratory Technician apprentices, perhaps the only thing bigger than Stephen's portfolio is his heart.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 114

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Technicians

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Birds, Isabel

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

As the research technician for the Aspden lab, Tayah Hopes has made innumerable contributions to our research, our knowledge and skills, and to the running of the lab. Her lab management skills are absolutely key to our success; from managing the numerous affairs of a newly established lab, to coordinating our move to a new building, to supporting us through a pandemic. She plans meticulously to get us organised ahead of time, whilst constantly working to improve processes in the lab. For example, when the lab was using an excess of plastic micropestles for genotyping CRISPR flies, she researched how to decontaminate them so they could be reused, reducing the environmental impact of the research. Tayah's generosity in collaboration is second to none, sharing both her knowledge and time. She is an amazing and patient teacher of techniques, transferring fundamental wet-lab skills to new members, and more specialised assays such as polysome profiling to collaborators internally and externally. She puts thought into how she can contribute to everyone's projects, whether that's sharing tried and tested protocols, or sharing the burden of long days of *Drosophila* dissection. Further, Tayah is extremely knowledgeable, and applies this knowledge to adapt existing protocols to different tissues and sample types. Her quick thinking, ingenuity and 6+ year long lab experience has made her the go-to person for troubleshooting advice. We often deal with small samples that take weeks of collection, and Tayah can always utilise them to their best potential. In particular, her encyclopaedic knowledge of RT-qPCR is invaluable in an RNA focused lab, as is her insight in journal clubs and group meetings. To conclude, Tayah has outstanding technical skills and knowledge that she is constantly working to share with others. The true impact of her work on research is immeasurable.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 124

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Data stewards and managers

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Gage, Jacob

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Avtar joined London Business School halfway through the REF2021 period in an Academic Services Manager role and was soon facing a number of REF related challenges. To deliver REF2021 Avtar: • Led the implementation of a new CRIS systems which was critical to the REF submission quickly becoming the system expert with the institution • Translated REF OA policy requirements; clarified & developed key aspects of the institutional narrative through an internal promotional drive ("School Research DNA") • Brought in new data and analytical techniques to produce visualisations that focused effort, highlighted areas of focus and maintained staff morale. • Identified and championed successful technical and workflows initiatives to improve existing IR to maximise REF OA compliance • Enthused and challenged Library and Research Office colleagues throughout REF period to deliver best possible OA compliance profile • Developed and produced regular high-quality OA compliance reports for senior staff and faculty stakeholders • Demonstrably a very 'quick study' - developed and maintaining highly effective relationships with Research Office and faculty at all levels alongside working with IT project management and technical developers / implementers (external suppliers external & internal colleagues)

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 132

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role
Hidden role: Data stewards and managers
Role submitted: n/a
Name: Hindley, Nick
Organisation/University: N/A
Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A
Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Dear Sir or Madam, I'd like to submit Jaqui Farrar of the University Of East Anglia for this award. I have had the pleasure to work with Jaqui for the past 3 years initially as my immediate manager where she also headed up our finance reporting function as well as the data requirements and organisation for the UEA REF submission. I have worked within the NHS and the Army so have had some experience with large scale organisations and Jaqui is one of the best organisers and managers of people I have worked with. She is leaving the UEA later this year as she's retiring after another successful REF submission and I feel some wider recognition of her excellent work would be fitting. Kind Regards Nick

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A
Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A
Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 133

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: RMAs (Research Managers and Administrators)

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Matthew, Jacqueline

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

It is my pleasure to nominate Dr. Silvia Giamiperi, a much respected Clinical and Research Project Manager for a large multidisciplinary basic sciences and clinical translation project at King's College London. Over the last 4 years, Silvia has provided skillful professional and strategic leadership, with an energy, optimism, and enthusiasm that has never waned. Silvia's personable style has seen her excel in her role, providing clear direction, organised and efficient project delivery, plus setting the culture and fertile environment for a highly successful, collaborative, international, and multi-institutional team of scientists, engineers, clinicians, patients, and commercial partners. Now in its seventh year, the intelligent fetal imaging and diagnosis (iFIND) project aims to substantially improve the accuracy of antenatal fetal scans with advanced ultrasound/MRI, machine learning, and robotic technology. Silvia has embedded herself in the science beyond what her role calls for. She is forward-thinking, whilst also working in the background to support innovative clinical translation successes such as the world's first clinical fetal cardiac MRI service, built on a foundation of iFIND research outputs. Indeed, Silvia's commitment to the professional success of others has seen a growing cadre of successful independent researchers going on to achieve prestigious fellowships, grants or related industry roles. Whilst keeping the iFIND project's complex work packages and ambitious milestones financially and strategically on track, Silvia has shown a grace and art in managing multiple stakeholders including senior academics, early career researchers, professional services personnel, and more. Now in a technology clinical translation phase, Silvia's flexibility and dynamism has seen her contribute to Public Engagement activities, organise End User events, provide training opportunities and share her deepening knowledge about Intellectual Property and commercialisation. Despite this, her role goes unrecognised in traditional REF research outputs and I truly welcome this opportunity to nominate her for this award.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 135

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Technicians

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Goense, Jozien

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Lindsay Gallagher is a highly skilled research technician who has worked at the University of Glasgow for over 30 years. She is recognized externally as a leading expert in animal models of stroke and is regularly contacted by other researchers to assist in training or provide technical advice in model development. Over the course of her career she has trained >100 PhD students & postdocs in surgical models of stroke, anesthesia, and general surgical skills. She has made significant technical and intellectual contributions to a large number of studies, evidenced by the 21 publications where she is listed as an author. In addition, she has been integral in the development of refinements to the surgical models of stroke, resulting in improved results as well as improved welfare of the animals. This has resulted in her contributing to the development of standard operating procedures for stroke surgery as part of a large pre-clinical stroke network (Percie du Sert et al, 2017). She continues to develop her technical knowledge and skills, where she researches the literature for students and troubleshoots and sets up new techniques. Recent examples include setting up techniques for measuring glymphatic flow, vessel permeability assessment for blood brain barrier breakdown, capnography for end tidal CO2 measurements & new anesthesia paradigms for functional MRI and electrophysiology. In the last few years she has gotten very involved in Home Office related tasks. As we run pre-clinical imaging and surgical facilities, investigators from all across the university use our facility, using many different techniques on many different project licenses. Lindsay always helps investigators with any procedures and double-checks that everything complies with investigators' Home Office licenses and training records. In summary, Lindsay's tremendous expertise and helpfulness keeps us all right and I am incredibly grateful for that.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 145

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role
Hidden role: Research Software Engineers
Role submitted: n/a
Name: Clare, Stuart
Organisation/University: N/A
Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A
Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Matthew Webster, Paul McCarthy and Taylor Hanayik develop and support the FSL library of brain imaging analysis tools (<https://fsl.fmrib.ox.ac.uk>). This extensive suite of tools, originally developed by researchers at the Wellcome Centre for Integrative Neuroimaging, University of Oxford, are made freely available to the community, and are used to analyse MRI data from research and clinical scanners to provide statistically robust measures of brain size, structure, activity and connectivity. The tools have had 59,000 individual downloads over the past 2 years and are estimated to be used in over 5000 labs worldwide. With such a wide user base, for a free software tool, the team provide a vital hidden role in ensuring that the tools work across a variety of operating systems and versions, are easy to install and kept updated as new features or tools are devised and validated by the wider research team. Much of the user base support is provided via a public mailing list which had 4736 posts and 1332 unique threads during 2020. 1048 of these threads were responded to by one of this core team. In addition to the role in supporting the wider userbase, the team provide vital support to the 500 users within the University, offering day-to-day help and training via internal and external courses.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A
Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A
Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 146

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Other

Role submitted: Engineer

Name: Park, Naomi

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

This nomination is for Colin Barker (cb4@sanger.ac.uk). Colin uses his many years and wide breadth of experience to design and create bespoke equipment for scientists across the Institute. My role is to develop high throughput processes. I have faced problems I don't know how to solve – the solution is not something that can just be bought off the shelf. We can go to Colin who listens carefully and works with us to find a solution. He rapidly mocks up a prototype or a drawing keeping us involved. I have learnt from working alongside him and ended up with solutions matching just what was required. One such process, used for identifying insecticide resistance in mosquitos, required the use of a specific robot. We thought it did everything we needed, but a subsequent development was a requirement to hold plates at 4 C or the end result was seriously compromised. Colin came up with a solution to integrate into the robotic setup which is in use today. Another example is for SARs-CoV-2 pandemic surveillance sequencing. Samples are processed in 384 well plates. At certain process stages the seal of the plates must be removed – which is tricky as they are heat sealed. Their removal creates a risk of splashing which would lead to unusable data. Colin designed desealing stations to hold the plates firmly down on the bench whilst the seals are manually removed, increasing the amount of data generated. Colin works closely with staff members to involve them in any design – and in that way we become better scientists by understanding alternative engineering based ways to approach problems. He has been involved with public engagement, welcoming school visits into his workshop pre-pandemic. I am just one of many scientists Colin's work has significantly impacted and collectively deserves recognition!

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 147

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: RMAs (Research Managers and Administrators)

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Priston, Sarah

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

I am writing to nominate the REF Impact and repository team at Bath Spa University - Ms Rebecca Atkins, Dr Miranda Barnes and Dr Astrid Breel. Over the last two years they have supported our creative practice academics in the on-line documentation of their research practice. This has resulted in the development of a suite of e-portfolios which have been submitted to the REF as research outputs in our repository BathSPAdata (<https://data.bathspa.ac.uk/>). The bulk of these outputs have been published, and have enabled us to build up a range of material that showcases our creative practice research in a way that is new to the sector. We have worked closely with our repository provider - Figshare - to develop the content in the most appropriate way, and to ensure that the documentation is accessible to all. We have also developed some portfolios of evidence in support of our creative practice that underpin our impact case studies in relevant UoA areas, again making this material available to the public in a new and innovative fashion. We believe that we are a pioneer in this area, and the dedication of the team, and their collaborative working practices should be acknowledged. The research behind creative practice is often not showcased or easily accessible, and by developing a way to publish these electronically, we hope to foster a better understanding of creative arts practices, and to put them on a level footing to more traditional outputs of research. This nomination is in recognition of the skills demonstrated by the team in being able to make sense of the research process that underpins this work and explaining its cultural and societal impact in a format that reaches as wide an audience as possible, and raises the profile of world-leading creative practice.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 154

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role
Hidden role: Research Software Engineers
Role submitted: n/a
Name: Robinson, Martin
Organisation/University: N/A
Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A
Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Person Nominated: Dr Mihaela Duta, Senior Research Software Engineer at the Oxford Research Software Engineering (OxRSE) group at the University of Oxford (www.rse.ox.ac.uk) The Nuffield Early Language Intervention (NELI) is a programme demonstrated to improve oral language skills in young children, developed by a team at University of Oxford led by Professors Charles Hulme and Maggie Snowling. The NELI programme is part of the government response to the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on children's education. This school year, 62,000 reception-age pupils in over 6,000 schools in England whose language and literacy development had been most affected by the pandemic are taking part in the NELI programme to improve their language skills (tinyurl.com/hkzf6fnz). Further government funding continues the NELI rollout into the next school year when every state school with a Reception class in England will be offered access to the programme (tinyurl.com/a9tx3z4m). Dr Mihaela Duta has a key role in the NELI programme as the developer of LanguageScreen, a mobile application that gives education professionals a quick and accurate assessment of a child's language skills. LanguageScreen is used by teachers to identify pupils most likely to benefit from the NELI programme. Mihaela also collaborated with other RSEs from the OxRSE group to develop the first version of the server infrastructure (languagescreen.com) that manages school signups and assessment data from the LanguageScreen app. She also has a leading role in the technical integration of the LanguageScreen app and data collection server into the NELI programme. LanguageScreen is a cross-platform mobile app available from both Play Store (tinyurl.com/kywxya4) and App Store (<http://tinyurl.com/85n72dc7>). To date, LanguageScreen has been used to assess more than 180,000 reception school pupils.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A
Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A
Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 157

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Technicians

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Spaul, Steven

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Nominees: The R&D; team Nick Cole, George Ricketts, Peter Savage. The team supports concept discussions, costing, assembly and installation of manufactured components for researchers at the University of Exeter. Their combined work experience (>70 years) in academia and industry covers skills from materials science, parametric 3D design, 2D engineering drawings, to finite element analysis and manufacturing. The team expertly talks customers through the design process, highlights manufacturing limitations, and empowers the customer to improve their work. They produce quick, fit-for-purpose, cost-effective solutions that are fundamental to project successes: Hand warmer, Prof Stephens: "We measure the human body's metabolic response to various interventions and use hand warming units to sample arterialised blood. The team designed and built a new unit that works better than the original, allowing 13 PhD students and a postdoc to continue their research, and increasing our research capacity, income and outputs." Anechoic chamber, Dr Powell: "The team designed and constructed a state-of-the-art anechoic chamber for electromagnetic measurements out of a cold-storage freezer, saving hundreds of thousands of pounds compared to buying this setup. This chamber has been fundamental to at least three publications and several upcoming grant applications during the few months it has been operational." Laser guarding, Dr Keatley: "The team's laser enclosures design enabled the quick installation of our EXTREMAG facility laser safety infrastructure, expediting its use by local, national, and international researchers." Dr Sherlock: "The laser shielding made our custom-built nonlinear microscopes safe to use for researchers with no prior experience of working in a laser laboratory. This allowed us to broaden our research horizons and seek funding from new sources." Notable other impact: The team designed and built of a free-of-charge tampons/sanitary pads dispenser, utilising their skills and creativity to support an inclusive environment for our female students, staff, and visitors.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 159

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Other

Role submitted: The SP and CSE ARCHER Support Teams

Name: Smith, Lorna

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

ARCHER was the UK's National High Performance Computing service for over 7 years. This exceptional resource enabled world-class research, placing UK scientists at the forefront of computational science research. Over ARCHER's lifetime, just under 6.1 billion core hours were used for computation. To place this in context, a 4-core laptop with cores of comparable performance to the ARCHER cores, would take over 173,000 years to perform the same amount of computation as ARCHER did in its lifetime. ARCHER was delivered by the Service Provision (SP) and Computational Science and Engineering (CSE) teams. The teams enabled UK researchers to maximise their science output, through activities such as software installation, documentation, in-depth support, application development, query support and skills transfer through training course development and delivery. To deliver this service the teams of around 15 people, required a detailed technical knowledge of the ARCHER platform, strong software development skills, and an understanding of the science and aspirations of the user communities. Notable support highlights include:

- 57,489 contractual queries were resolved with 98.6% of them being completed within two days;
- Around 10 codes a month benefitted or were improved by the service through in-depth support;
- Around 7000 users accounts were created, forming our very broad user base including users from new communities;
- Provided around 450 days of training, with around 200 different courses. In 2019 alone over 1000 people registered for ARCHER courses.
- Organised the eCSE programme, a software development programme that allocated funding to Research Software Engineers (RSEs) embedded within research communities across the UK. The teams coordinated 13 calls, funded 100 projects across 46 institutions, and achieved over 5 times return on investment. The CSE and SP teams continue to support the UK computational science community in the delivery of world-leading science from ARCHER's successor, ARCHER2.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 166

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Other

Role submitted: Housing rights advisor

Name: Woodland, Michael

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Michael joined Toynbee Hall's private renters' project in autumn 2020. The group of peer researchers had conducted research into the challenges faced by young private renters in East London, the group were moving into a proposal co-design stage with landlords when Michael came on board. With a great deal of practical knowledge and experience, having worked on a London authority's housing team, Michael has become an invaluable asset to the project. During the proposal co-design stage, he provided insight and expertise in workshops, mediating between renters and landlords, elaborating on the rules and regulations that both parties need to legally adhere to. He also helped the peer researchers to assess and develop policy recommendations to improve the sector based on their research findings. As an expert in housing, he has played an important role in strengthening the participatory action research process.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Practices panel

Entry: 48

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: McConnell, Gail

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

The Plymouth Optical Microscopy Workshop has trained over 375 early career researchers and facility managers from more than 30 countries in advanced optical imaging for cell biology. The course, founded in 2003 by Dr Brad Amos, provides education in all aspects of optical imaging, from basic light microscopy and image formation to advanced techniques such as super-resolution microscopy and single molecule localisation methods. The course has admitted students purely on merit and need rather than ability to pay fees. This has been possible thanks to on-going industrial financial support from microscope vendors and awards from funding sources and learned societies including EMBO, the MRC and the Company of Biologists. Demand for one of the 25 places on the course is high, with up to 7 applicants per place available. The ratio of teaching staff to student attendees is 3:1, offering an unparalleled learning experience. Students receive lectures, but more than half of the course comprises hands-on practical work. Students work in small groups (no more than 4 students per group) to disassemble microscopes, learn specimen preparation methods, and use advanced microscopes. Students receive tuition in optical alignment: this demonstration has proven so successful that other international courses have launched their own version of our training package. Companies have frequently chosen the course as the venue to launch their latest microscopes, with students being the first to learn about exciting new developments in the field. Additionally, the unique location of the course at the historically important Marine Biological Association allows students to collect their own marine specimens from the coastline for imaging with the many microscopes available. Student feedback for the course has been excellent and the impacts long-term. More than 20 attendees now lead research groups worldwide, and their students are applying to the course to learn the latest methods.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 54

Applicant details

Submission category: 5 - Enabling access to facilities

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Findlay, Kim

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

I am nominating myself, as a technology platform manager at the John Innes Centre where I now head a team of 5 permanent staff with over 20 light and electron microscopes. From humble beginnings consisting of just a few instruments and me, I have been responsible for the growth and development of the facility. It was arguably the first true core-funded facility to emerge here, well over 25 years ago, and now supports scientists across the whole Norwich Research Park. As well as managing a team and providing technical support and training, I do electron microscopy myself as "service work". I was fully responsible for the design and layout of the new facilities when we moved buildings, working closely with the engineers and architects. I have been the driving force behind all new equipment purchases, writing all the funding bids with minimal input from others. Last year I won over £2M from BBSRC for two major capital projects in Bioimaging. Even though I wrote these bids, I am not recognised as the "project leader" on our databases. A senior manager has that glory, despite not adding anything more than his signature to the bid before submission. I take responsibility for purchasing and overseeing successful installations in the facility. Such equipment is a huge asset for our institute and enables a great deal of high quality science. For light microscopy, my team help assess the market, test equipment and arrange for install, but the funding bids are still written by me. For electron microscopy, which is my area of expertise, I take full responsibility. Such high-value bids and installations are often extremely complex. I am sure there are many other facility managers who also do not get adequate recognition for their efforts in winning major amounts of funding for equipment.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 60

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Devlin, Marie

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Pedagogical research in a discipline such as Computing is not recognised as ref-able. I run a research group at my university on Educational Practice in Computing. Innovations from my group include new methods to teach Software Engineering, teamwork, to assess and give feedback on programming, to encourage reflection and development of metacognition to combat the compartmentalisation that modules bring to almost every HE discipline etc. My group publish papers, give talks, develop software and contribute to a growing community of practitioners in the UK and the international arena. We are part of the first UK chapter of ACM SIGCSE - there are few funding streams and little recognition of the work that we do in promotion processes, yet we conduct the research all the same because we believe in what we do and that it can change practice and the student experience, for the better. My School and University have gone some way to recognise our efforts but promotion processes still remain difficult, many teaching-only academic staff and teaching technicians are on low paid and (until recently) temporary contracts with little hope of a clear career path. There is little funding for PhD studentships in the UK or EU in the area yet these are in great demand from international students. It would be nice if this research was recognised as valid given the increased need for technical skills in the workforce and in schools and for recognition of the benefits brought by expertise shared with others nationally and internationally.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 63

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: McGregor, Nora

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

For nearly a decade now, the British Library's ground-breaking Digital Scholarship Training Programme (DSTP) has helped information professionals develop skills necessary to support, and undertake in their own right, computationally driven research with cultural heritage collections. In 2012, BL Digital Curators developed this new and unique curriculum to introduce staff to the cutting-edge tools and methodologies of digital scholarship, and their application in the cultural heritage context. Originally planned as a distinct series of intensive one-day courses, alongside a series of '21st Century Curatorship' talks, the DSTP has expanded to include monthly informal 'Hack-and-Yacks' and a reading group to meet an ever growing demand for digital scholarship skills. Event programming and participation has grown year-on-year and in the last 12 months alone, the DSTP delivered 58 events to 408 individuals. Consistently excellent feedback indicates the programme responds to the evolving demands of their jobs, while the proliferation of practical applications, from data wrangling and analysis to handwritten text recognition, case studies and digital scholarship collaborations by attendees strongly demonstrates impact and value. Building on years of experience, in 2020, the DSTP took its first official foray into delivering training to an external audience through the development of a PGCert course in Computing for Cultural Heritage. In collaboration with Birkbeck University, The National Archives and Institute for Coding, this course provides cultural professionals with coding knowledge that can be directly applied to their jobs. Attendees have since gone on to undertake data science projects such as analysing catalogue descriptions of health-related archival resources to improve understanding of a historic epidemic. The DSTP has effectively disseminated information to thousands of British Library staff and sector professionals, allowing them to undertake innovative digital work. DSTP is an evolving, responsive and impactful service, highly successful in translating important new methodologies to support scholars.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 74

Applicant details

Submission category: 7 - Standards

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Rossi, Giulia Carla

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

The British Library's Emerging Formats Project builds capacity for collecting digital publications whose formats are more complex than current collection items. It responds to UK Non-Print Legal Deposit Regulations (2013); we needed to develop new technical capabilities and workflows to collect digital-only publications otherwise at risk of loss. We have addressed the impact of technology on writing and reading, researcher needs for digital collections, and rapid obsolescence of digital formats. The project has increased the capabilities of cultural organisations to identify, collect, describe and preserve complex digital publications. We produced a definition of 'emerging formats' that includes ebook apps for mobile devices, web-based interactive narratives and structured data, produced by a diverse range of content creators. Through in-depth research, we defined user needs for accessing this content. This included a need for curated collections, support for contextual information, and new types of library access environments to increase the authenticity of the experience of using digital publications. For example, these may depend on mobile devices with cameras, gyroscopes or running on particular operating systems. Using UK Web Archive tools, we built a living collection of 200 web-based interactive narratives. This comprises various works created using different platforms alongside contextual information to aid researchers' understanding. In addition, involvement in the New Media Writing Prize has enabled the preservation of both winning and shortlisted entries. The ongoing Emerging Formats Project has made significant strides towards enabling the future research landscape, making innovative publications more easily accessible to researchers. The project has influenced conversations among collecting institutions, academics and creative industry practitioners. We have hosted multiple creative residencies, summer schools and AHRC-funded doctoral placements. Additionally, outcomes have been shared widely through international conferences (iPres, ICIDS) and in highly-read journals such as Alexandria, and most recently through contributing expertise to the AHRC-funded COPIM project.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 88

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Cohen, Jeremy

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Training material for the Singularity container platform Overview: Singularity (<https://github.com/sylabs/singularity>) is a container platform that enables the running of containers within user space on Linux systems. Its design makes it ideal for use in shared High Performance Computing (HPC) environments. Indeed, Singularity has been gaining significant traction within the research community, being deployed on a wide range of HPC infrastructure including the UK's National Supercomputing Service, ARCHER2. For researchers without a computational science background, just understanding and using HPC infrastructure can present a technical barrier. The addition of containerisation adds a further layer of complexity. Nonetheless, containers are an important element in supporting reproducibility and software portability. Jeremy Cohen (Imperial) and Andy Turner (EPCC) have produced a set of Singularity training material to help researchers develop core skills for using the platform. The material: The material (<https://carpentries-incubator.github.io/singularity-introduction/>) has been developed in the Carpentries lesson template and takes learners through the basics of getting started with Singularity. It looks at running containers from Singularity's container registry, Singularity Hub, and running commands for managing and working with containers. It then shows how Docker containers, from Docker Hub, can be run via Singularity. The second part of the material looks at more advanced topics including building containers and running them on HPC platforms via job scripts, including the running of MPI parallel jobs. Availability: The material is openly available under a CC-BY 4.0 licence and anyone is welcome to use the material, modify it and also contribute local changes into the master copy of the lesson material. Future development: The lesson material has been accepted into the Carpentries Incubator (<https://carpentries.org/community-lessons/#the-carpentries-incubator>) where it is undergoing further development, overseen by a team of maintainers. The long-term plan is to continue to enhance the material with a view to it potentially becoming a core carpentries lesson.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 90

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Cohen, Jeremy

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Reproducible Computational Environments using Containers Overview: Containers are playing an increasingly important role in the management of research software. They support reproducibility and can simplify distribution of complex software pipelines. They also support long-term sustainability since container images can be archived through services such as Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>). Working with containers does, however, require some level of technical knowledge and for many researchers, understanding container concepts and the tools used to create and run them can be challenging. Andy Turner (EPCC) and Jeremy Cohen (Imperial) have developed a course that trains participants in the basics of two widely used container platforms - Docker and Singularity. Course materials: The course content (e.g. <https://imperialcollegelondon.github.io/2020-07-13-Containers-Online/>) is a combination of open material developed by other researchers and modified or extended by the course organisers (Docker), as well as material that the organisers have developed from scratch (Singularity) and made openly available. It provides an introduction to containers, what they are, how they work and how to use both Docker and Singularity to run and build containers. Course structure: The course consists of 4 hours of material on each of Docker and Singularity. The material has been taught online, as a two-day course, running 10:00-12:00 and 14:00-16:00 on both days. This ensures lengthy breaks and helps manage online fatigue. Teaching: The organisers ran the Reproducible Computational Environments using Containers course twice in 2020 with plans to run the course again in 2021 due to significant interest. The course was supported by EPCC and PRACE and the second run of the course used ARCHER2 for teaching Singularity. Future development: The materials used for the course are now part of the Carpentries Incubator and will undergo a managed process of further development and maintenance. The course organisers have been collaborating with original developers of material where relevant.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 99

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Karoune, Emma

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Submission by The Turing Way Community: The Turing Way's goal is to provide all the information that researchers need at the start of their projects to ensure that they are easy to reproduce at the end. It is an open-source project that involves and supports its diverse community to make data science reproducible, ethical, collaborative and inclusive for everyone. The project was conceived and is led by Kirstie Whitaker, the lead of the Tools, Practices and Systems Programme at The Alan Turing Institute. The Community Manager, Malvika Sharan, plays an important role in bringing together the community at regular events and nurturing contributions to the ever-expanding resource, an online book. The book currently has five guides (Reproducibility, Project Design, Communication, Collaboration and Ethical Research), and a Community handbook. Each guide is a work in progress, as we encourage everyone to keep adding to this resource. However, The Turing Way is much more than a book: it is a community of practice based around the moonshot goal of making reproducible research 'too easy not to do'. The outputs belong to The Turing Way community and everyone can freely read, reuse, distribute, modify, and contribute back to the resources in the book. The project is built on open source infrastructure such as Git, Jupiter Book and Netlify. We foster a culture of collaboration through being explicit that our project is open for contributions in many different ways, and enabling an inclusive workspace by providing a clear code of practice and contributing guidelines. Our community is global and contributors come from a diverse range of scientific disciplines. There are currently over 250 direct Github contributors and more than 5000 unique users monthly. The project is also influencing other research communities such as The Health Foundation, UKRI Innovation Scholars, Open Research Handbooks at Reading and York universities, and more.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 104

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Wall, Natalie

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

The Research Impact Team at Queen Mary University of London has developed a comprehensive and culture-building portfolio of training workshops, drop-ins and one-to-one engagements. This includes a mix of team- and individual-taught workshops, and both general-purpose and one-off bespoke sessions for individual schools and other specialised audiences. In response to the institution's strategic direction in impact and knowledge exchange beyond REF 2021, the Impact Team developed nine new workshops (including "Evaluating and Evidencing Impact," "Reaching your Stakeholders through the Media & Social Media", "Navigating Policy Impact," "Impact from Public Engagement", "Achieving Commercial/Industrial Impact" and "Impact Leadership") while working to integrate online support applications and tools like Blackboard Collaborate, Zoom, MS Teams, Mentimeter, and Padlet. Interest in research impact training has spiked alongside the University's staff having more flexible schedules, resulting in an outstandingly successful training year. In the past year, despite the challenges posed by COVID-19, the Impact Team has trained 767 staff and research students, twice as many as the previous year. Since September 2020, three extra sessions have had to be run due to oversubscription. One of the best-received and most successful items in the impact team's training schedule is the annual PhD Cohort 2 (Impact) day (for second-year doctoral students), run in conjunction with Queen Mary's Doctoral College. According to Mentimeter polls taken during the 2021 event, its effect on the students' understanding of impact was transformative: at the start of the session, only 18 out of 58 (31%) of respondents considered themselves to have a working knowledge of impact ("I get by"), with the remainder either unfamiliar with the term or unsure how it related to them. By the end of the session, virtually all students (57/60 or 95%) felt confident they had a working knowledge of impact, with 3 respondents (5%) now considering themselves "expert."

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 106

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Karmakharm, Twin

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Recent advances in deep neural networks coupled with an increasing amount and complexity of scientific data collected in a wide array of domains provide many exciting opportunities for deep learning applications in scientific settings. There has been great interest from researchers in how this can be applied practically to their field. In response to this we created a new Introduction to Deep Learning course which provides an introduction to regression and classification using neural networks, image classification with convolutional neural networks and speeding up the training process of models using existing neural networks. The course has a significant practical element to the course and is delivered online with the use of Google Colab notebooks. The course is a 1 day workshop (8 hours) that's available in both Python and R. The materials are open sourced and publicly available through the github repository (<https://github.com/rses-dl-course/rses-dl-course.github.io>) and hosted on Github pages (<https://rses-dl-course.github.io/>). So far we've run 2 of each Python and R workshops with a total of 140 attendees with very positive feedback from the majority. With all courses being fully subscribed, we are scheduled to run the training regularly in the future.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 110

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Krystalli, Anna

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Reproducibility is a fundamental tenet of research and while the academic community now has accepted the requirement for producibility of computational research, there is little training available to researchers to develop the skills required. Instead, it is still common in academia for programming skills to be self-taught - this can come at the expense of proficiency when it comes to project management and best practice, and ultimately the reproducibility and reusability of published research code and data. For the last 6 years Dr Anna Krystalli has taught a hands-on intensive course for first-year ACCE DTP PhD students at the Universities of Sheffield, York & Leeds. Based in the R programming language, a popular tool in biological research, the first day of the course provides basic R training, which forms a foundation for 3 more days covering data management, reproducible project design and management, version control, literate programming, packaging code and creating reproducible research compendia. Underlying all training is to confer best practice from a research software engineering perspective and ultimately to empower students to produce more robust, reproducible and reusable outputs rather than them feeling swamped by increased requirements with respect to the reproducibility of their work. Following the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic in March 2020, the last two iterations of this programme have been successfully delivered online. Materials for the course are themselves reproducible and can be found publicly at <https://annakrystalli.me/rrresearchACCE20/>

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 116

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Tartarini, Daniele

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Computer simulations are considered the third leg of the scientific method. In many domains simulations would have meaning only if performed at a very high resolution and in a reasonable timeline. Computer manufacturers are pushing the technology to the physical limit to achieve performance on the exascale level. This is being achieved by introducing massive parallel architectures (GPUs in particular) and new programming paradigms requiring a steep learning curve for the researchers and research software developer. The GPU hackathon is an initiative organised by The University of Sheffield and nVIDIA, the leading manufacturer of GPUs: <https://gpuhack.shef.ac.uk/>. Research teams around the world are invited to apply to participate in this hackathon where for a week they are trained and helped in redesign their application to better translate their software to exploit the computational power of GPUs. This initiative has a strong hands-on character and is run every year supporting between 6 and 10 groups. They are paired with GPU specialised engineers from Sheffield and nVidia that help analysing and restructuring their code to achieve the best performance.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 130

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Keating, Connor

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

The Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training (FORRT) addresses the underappreciated pedagogical aspect of open and reproducible science and its associated challenges, including a need for curricular reform, an account of epistemological pluralism, the development of new methods of education, and questions around how open science practices relate to social justice and a principled academic education. Teachers' and researchers' time constraints are substantial, posing a challenge to developing course materials and integrating new research practices in teaching. FORRT develop strategies and propose solutions to mitigate time constraints and help scholars implement open and principled education in their workflows. That's why we created FORRT's e-learning platform (or Nexus), a hub for community-driven initiatives and resources. Elements of the Nexus are: FORRT's Clusters (a pedagogically-driven organization of OS literature), Curated Resources (database of >1000 resources on OS), Initiatives Towards Social Justice in Academia (where we link mentees of unprivileged backgrounds to mentors of privileged ones), Open & Reproducible Science Summaries (having more than 220 summaries of OS literature), 7-ways to adopt principled teaching and mentoring practices (listing 100+ low commitment ways to interact with OS), Open & Reproducible Science Syllabus (a boiler-plate template for OS course that can be readily adapted and implemented in teachers' courses), Self-Assessment Tool (a dynamic survey giving teachers feedback on how to integrate OS into their teaching), and finally, Educator's Corner (offering a platform for educators of all stripes to share their stories, experiences, successes and hardships in teaching and mentoring, as well as for sharing educational practices and initiatives that are of interest to the OS community). FORRT's community conceptualized the Educational Nexus as integrating diverse components into one infrastructure serving those wishing to learn, adopt, and disseminate open and reproducible science tenets.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 136

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Elsherif, Mahmoud

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

The Open Science movement is becoming more prevalent. In line with the Open Science Movement, new research and literature is being produced. However, the literature is now voluminous, and the manuscripts are becoming lengthy, making it difficult to digest and implement open and reproducible science with pedagogy. In turn, more time and effort are expended to stay up-to-date and try to educate future consumers of science. This adds a substantial amount of work on top of the teachers' and researchers' time constraints, posing a challenge to develop course materials and integrate new research practices in teaching. The Framework of Open Reproducible Research and Teaching (FORRT) community has prepared 200+ summaries of Open and Reproducible Science literature that can be integrated into taught courses. The purpose of the summaries is to reduce some of the burden on educators looking to incorporate open and reproducible research principles into their teaching, as well as facilitate the edification of anyone wishing to learn or disseminate open and reproducible science tenets. In addition, the goal of creating summaries was to foster social justice through democratization of scientific educational resources and pedagogies. FORRT has made a distinction between "Open and Reproducible Science" summaries and "Diversity, Equity, & Inclusion" summaries to highlight that the topics of social injustices and DEI (diversity, equity and inclusion) are often neglected in academia, and in open and reproducible science literature. The summaries allow us to relate social justice to open science practices and how to best support scholars in their efforts to learn and stay knowledgeable on best practices regarding open and reproducible research. Moreover, summaries are meant to facilitate conversations about the ethics and social impact of teaching substantive topics with regard to scientific openness, social justice, epistemic uncertainty and the credibility revolution.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 137

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Herrera, Juan

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

The ARCHER2 training programme covers many subject areas, levels of technical expertise, approaches to training, and delivery mechanisms. We have designed a training programme that addresses the training requirements of users with different needs and level of experience. Our goal is to deliver a training programme that meets the demands of users of HPC research software as well as those who develop it. The ARCHER2 training programme offers: - Core, transferable skills in computational and data science including The Carpentries courses. - Three courses covering how to use ARCHER2 specifically targeted at Software Package users, Data Scientists, and Developers. - Using the most popular research software packages at introductory, intermediate, and advanced levels. - Intermediate and advanced HPC programming techniques and topics including MPI, OpenMP, parallel IO, and containers for HPC. - Applied data science tools and techniques, including using data analysis packages, machine/deep learning packages, and data processing frameworks such as Spark. An overview of the provided courses as part of the ARCHER2 service can be found here:

<https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/courses/> A regular programme of Virtual Tutorials (VTs) is also delivered, where experts can share their knowledge on a range of intermediate and advanced topics during interactive live webinars. Appropriate ARCHER2 courses are available via a self-service model, where they have been specifically tailored to be followed at a user's own pace. For instance, the course entitled "Shared Memory Programming with OpenMP" is offered as self-service:

<https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/courses/210000-openmp-self-service/> Since April 2020, a total of 66 training days were delivered between courses and VTs. Attendance details can be found on the ARCHER2 Quartely reports listed here: <https://www.archer2.ac.uk/about/reports/> Material from all online courses, including videos of the lectures, is freely available on the web after the live run. It is listed here: <https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/materials/>

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 152

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Konovalov, Alexander

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

The GAP Carpentries-style lesson had been initiated by Alexander Konovalov in 2015 for the training programme of CCP-CoDiMa (<https://www.codima.ac.uk/training/>). The latest released version with contributions by Michael Torpey and Christopher Jefferson, based on the Carpentries lesson template by its respective contributors, is archive on Zenodo. The lesson is now move to the Carpentries incubator (<https://carpentries-incubator.github.io/gap-lesson/>) with the repository at <https://github.com/carpentries-incubator/gap-lesson>. The lesson has been taught at least 14 events see the list at <https://github.com/carpentries-incubator/gap-lesson/wiki> in UK, Germany, France and Nigeria by at least 8 instructors, and was well received as shown by the feedback linked from the linked Wiki page. Estimating a average event attendance between 20 and 25 learners, that's between 280 and 350 learners trained, not counting those who learned it by self-study, e.g. discovering it on Mathematics Stackexchange site (<https://math.stackexchange.com/questions/104195/which-resources-are-available-to-self-study-gap/369307#369307>).

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 162

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Harris, Sian

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Most research is published in the global North but many of the world's most urgent problems are in the South. Researchers in low and middle-income countries (LMICs) face many challenges in communicating their work, including lack of familiarity with global scholarly publishing; lack of experienced colleagues to advise on publishing; inexperience of scientific writing; and language barriers, in addition to inherent biases in global scholarship. In 2015 INASP's AuthorAID project started running free research-writing massive open online courses (MOOCs) on Moodle. Courses are designed to be appropriate to the context of participants. Many countries struggle with low internet bandwidth and intermittent power so courses are designed to be bandwidth efficient, have resources that are usable offline, and optimised for mobile devices. MOOC delivery is supported by a network of facilitators around the world, some of whom were previous course participants. To date, 27,558 early-career researchers in LMICs have benefitted from support in research writing via the courses. In 2020 our three research writing MOOCs had a total of 7,265 participants. AuthorAID MOOCs are particularly effective at reaching women researchers, who can find travel to face-to-face training harder due to childcare commitments and cultural expectations. We have also seen participants from fragile and conflict countries, as well as researchers who self-identify as refugees. Such support is essential for ensuring equity in global research. AuthorAID MOOCs have an average completion rate of 48%, very high for MOOCs, and close to 50:50 gender participation. Respondents report a 50% increase in research writing confidence on completion. We often hear from researchers about the difference that participation has had to them, their academic careers, their colleagues, and their ability to share their research findings clearly with a wider audience, locally and nationally. It has also led participants to run their own training within their institutions.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 163

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Coskeran, Helen

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

We would like to submit to this competition a suite of training materials created by ten research management professionals based in Botswana, South Africa, the UK and Zambia. The materials were created for a workshop series entitled 'Cradle to Grave: A Research and Programme Management Knowledge-sharing Series' supported by the International Research Management Staff Development Programme (IRSMDP), an initiative of the African Academy of Sciences and the Association of Research Managers and Administrators. The series ran in February-March 2021 and took 40 participants from across the globe (selected from a total of 180 applicants) through the life cycle of a programme. The series explored this in three stages: the first session examined the pre-award design process and proposal development, providing guidance in supporting academics with identifying and pursuing funding opportunities. The second session focused on how best to establish reporting frameworks for implementing collaborative research projects focusing on challenges and considerations associated with equitable partnerships, financial management, communication and data management. The third and final session included key considerations when finalising programme implementation and an in-depth discussion on ensuring legacy and accountability to a range of stakeholders. This included best practice in establishing monitoring, evaluation and learning frameworks at the outset that can help underpin such efforts. The skills and knowledge shared were in high demand, based on the number of applications received alone. A cohort of 40 participants was selected to allow for maximum interaction during the sessions but the resulting recordings and slide packs are being made publicly available. All 180 applicants are also being invited to join an international research managers' network. Providing upskilling and networking opportunities to professionals in this burgeoning sector is essential to research, both in supporting researchers in designing and implementing effective programmes and also to create learning for others in the profession.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 165

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Williams, Matt

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Over the last few years I have written a number of workshops which me and my colleagues have put on for staff and postgraduate students at the University of Bristol. Our target is primarily on PhD students and post-docs in order to train them in best practices for writing software, doing data analysis and collaborating with researchers. I have written courses on Python, data analysis, deep learning, machine learning, testing, and debugging. Particularly the introductory Python and data analysis courses are core to a large section of research that is performed as being able to extract simple answers from data, visualise it, and to do so in a reproducible and sustainable way enables all research. In the 2020/2021 academic year we taught over 1800 workshop spaces across around 60 3-hour workshops and in the years before that we were teaching hundreds of workshop spaces per year. It had been seen at Bristol and at other Universities that there is a lack of training available for these skills to postgraduate and post-doctoral researchers and the demand for the courses has only grown in the four years I have been giving them. The feedback has been excellent (<https://www.bristol.ac.uk/acrc/research-software-engineering/training/training-feedback/>) and have been told that the training has been essential to many people's research. All the material is freely available on-line for anyone to learn from, and it is this material that I am primarily submitting (<https://milliams.com/courses/>). Many of the workshops have also been recorded and are available as YouTube videos (<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL-LLaHO6rLYR6SUUHoHuyAmVxXFqNsv2F>) with a total of around 25 thousand views.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Contexts panel

Entry: 37

Applicant details

Submission category: 6 - Community Building

Role submitted: n/a

Name: n/a, n/a

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

www.digitalholocaustmemory.com shares research and provides networking space for individuals and organisations interested in digital Holocaust memory. Its launch in April 2020 was particularly timely as this month saw the commemoration of the 75th anniversaries of the last Nazi concentration camps, events for which were hastily transformed into online provisions. Since the launch, the website has hosted 5 online discussions featuring academics, and Holocaust museum and archive professionals, from the USA, UK, the Netherlands, Denmark, Germany, Poland, Serbia, Israel, South Africa and Australia, each attended by between 65-127 people. It has published a further 20 blog posts, mostly written by its founder and curator Dr. Victoria Grace Walden (University of Sussex) but also including guest posts by PhD students in the UK and Germany. It publishes a crowd-sourced and regularly updated academic reading list on digital Holocaust memory. In late 2020, it also established a Discord server for academics and creatives thinking about Holocaust memory and computer games. The server's moderator team of 10 includes academics and professionals from Germany, the USA, UK and India. In the 8 months since its incarceration, the website has attracted 11,982 views from 6,840 unique visitors from 87 nations. It has 560 people on its mailing list and 64 followers on WordPress or Email. It has 808 Twitter and 477 Facebook followers. The work on the site has led to a number of initiatives: (1) an advisory board for a Holocaust computer game, bringing together museum professionals, educators, academics, a survivor and an LA-based games company. (2) an edited collection and journal special edition together with 30 collaborators. (3) virtual talks for Cape Town Holocaust and Genocide Centre, ITSC, Lille, the University of Oxford, Univeristy of Haifa, Hebrew University, and Falstad Concentration Camp Memorial, Norway, and collaborations with colleagues at Yale and Bergen-Belsen.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 42

Applicant details

Submission category: 4 - Citizen Science

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Collinson, Lucy

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

The Etchiverse: working with volunteers to segment electron microscopy data The Etchiverse is a collection of online citizen science projects created by Dr Martin Jones and Dr Helen Spiers at the Francis Crick Institute, London. To date, multiple Etchiverse projects have been developed and launched, including 'Etch A Cell', 'Etch A Cell – Powerhouse Hunt' and 'Etch A Cell – VR'. Each of these projects asks volunteers to contribute to real research through segmenting organelles in electron microscopy data online. The creation of these citizen science projects has become necessary because of the rapid speed at which data is now acquired in volume electron microscopy. Manual segmentation remains the gold standard approach for data analysis, however, as this process is inherently slow, expert microscopists are unable to keep up with data production rates. This portfolio of projects has already achieved diverse outputs. Our projects have enabled a global community of thousands of volunteers to connect with and contribute to real and important research questions. This engagement has already generated tangible and impactful results. Critically, we have demonstrated that non-expert effort can produce high-quality segmentations. In our first Etch A Cell project, we worked with >4500 volunteers who together contributed >100,000 segmentations of the nuclear envelope (NE), representing >5000 hours of effort. The volunteer data produced was able to train a highly accurate machine learning algorithm able to segment the NE in a matter of minutes, rather than the many hours required for manual segmentation. Beyond these outputs, we have broadened the potential impact of this work by openly sharing all data and code, including benchmark volume EM data and volunteer/expert/machine NE segmentations. The success of this first project has directly catalysed the development of multiple new citizen science projects, emerging from new collaborations with national and international research teams.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 53

Applicant details

Submission category: 6 - Community Building

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Madden, Frances

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

FREYA (2017-2020), successfully built an international community that has significantly improved the uptake of persistent identifiers (PIDs), an essential component of scholarly communications. The project received EU funding and the project consortium included the British Library, EMBL-EBI and STFC from the UK. FREYA produced new research infrastructure centred on PIDs to improve the discovery and linking of resources by researchers, administrators and machines. Most importantly, we fostered an active community of users around these technical outputs, empowered to champion and employ PIDs in diverse contexts. FREYA adopted a nuanced communications approach responding to stakeholder needs, and delivered dissemination, engagement and training activities. This enabled initial PID adoption among some groups, and in-depth technical/practical guidance among others. Launching PIDForum.org enabled iterative engagement with a wide community of 500 members. Training resources were significantly improved based on feedback: these are downloaded 10,000 times per month from over 40 countries. Nearly 100 events and webinars received consistently strong engagement, with 10-15 members in focused workshops and audiences of >100 in wider public events. Recordings of these have >4000 views. Qualitative feedback demonstrated that participants found them useful and helped to build a baseline level of community engagement. Further community building was achieved through an ambassador programme with two-way collaboration. This strongly improved the PID skills of 37 individuals from 21 countries (on 6 continents), while their local expertise helped make FREYA services more relevant. Ambassadors widened the reach of resources by translating them into languages including Arabic, Portuguese, Slovakian and Ukrainian; these have been used >1500 times. Importantly, surveys indicated positive experiences and PID adoption in local communities was enhanced. Ultimately, FREYA demonstrated the importance of community building in rolling out scholarly communication resources, not only for building relevant services but for ensuring best practices are filtered down to diverse disciplinary/geographical communities.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 65

Applicant details

Submission category: 6 - Community Building

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Cohen, Jeremy

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Imperial College London Research Software Community Overview: Imperial's Research Software Community (<https://www.imperial.ac.uk/computational-methods/rse/>) is a grassroots community of researchers, RSEs, software engineers and individuals in a variety of other roles who are interested in or developing research software. Started in 2015, the community's primary aim is to raise awareness of the important role robust and sustainable research software plays in supporting high-quality research. It also recognises the cross-cutting nature of research software development, bringing together individuals based in departments across Imperial. Due to the somewhat siloed nature of many research domains, these individuals may otherwise never come into contact despite many of them tackling similar, often complex, technical challenges to support researchers in their field of work. Set up and led by Jeremy Cohen, the community is managed by a committee of researchers and RSEs and maintains key links with individuals and groups across the College, including, since its set up, the College's central RSE team. Aims: The community aims to provide knowledge exchange, training and networking opportunities as well as advice on applying best practices when building research software. It advocates for the importance of high-quality research software and related benefits, including reproducibility and sustainability, at all levels within the College. Membership: The community maintains a mailing list with over 200 members and a Slack workspace with over 240 members (there is significant but not complete crossover between the two groups). Activities and achievements: The community runs a wide range of events from technical talks followed by networking to training and workshops on both domain-specific and general technical topics. A monthly newsletter is published, which is now on its 28th issue (<https://imperialcollegelondon.github.io/rs-community-newsletters/>). It is felt that the community has played a significant and vitally important role over recent years in raising and maintaining awareness of research software engineering at Imperial.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 66

Applicant details

Submission category: 6 - Community Building

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Cohen, Jeremy

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Research Software London (RSLondon) Overview: RSLondon (<https://rslondon.ac.uk>) was started in late 2018 as one of Jeremy Cohen's EPSRC RSE Fellowship activities. It is a grassroots regional community that aims to bring together researchers, RSEs and anyone interested in research software at institutions in the London and wider South East of England regions. RSLondon supports both individuals at large institutions with existing research software activities and at smaller institutions that may not have the opportunity to sustain a research software community. It is helping to upskill researchers and RSEs through training workshops and opportunities to share knowledge and skills. RSLondon is also helping to build new collaborations and offers scope to advocate for important RSE-related issues across the region. RSLondonSouthEast: Held at The Royal Society in early 2019 and 2020, but postponed in 2021 due to the pandemic, the community's flagship annual workshop has filled all 100 available places on both occasions. The event provides a packed schedule of keynotes, technical presentations, discussion sessions and networking opportunities and more than 20 different institutions have been represented among the attendees. Membership: Community membership is informal with events and activities open to anyone based at an institution within the region. The community mailing list of almost 100 people includes several members who are contacts for disseminating information more widely around their local institutions. Achievements: Both RSLondonSouthEast workshops received extremely positive feedback and helped raise the community's profile within the region. The 2020 workshop's poster session was supported by the Society of Research Software Engineering. A collaboration formed as a direct result of the community was awarded a grant from the Crick Partnership Networking Fund. As the first grassroots regional RSE community, RSLondon is also playing a role in helping to highlight the importance of regional communities and providing a model for their development.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 70

Applicant details

Submission category: 4 - Citizen Science

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Clements, Dylan

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

The Dogslife project was launched in 2010 to follow a cohort of dogs over their lifecourse to identify the environmental and genetic risk factors for good health. Such a study had never been attempted before because of the cost and manpower burdens traditionally associated with this type of “big data” collection. By using a website-based questionnaire, and inviting owners to participate when they joined the Kennel Club, Dogslife developed a scalable and economic mechanism to collate data on canine health, lifestyle and morphology, whilst simultaneously educating participating dog owners about factors affecting dog health through the website and a monthly newsletter. To date, 8,000 dogs have joined the project, enabling the curation of a dataset with 68,000 health records detailing 35,000 illness episodes. Over time, the project has expanded to acquire additional data from participating dogs, including biological samples and image data. Dogslife is the first, and largest, longitudinal study of dog health, and has provided unique insights into the factors affecting it, including 1) environmental risks for adult canine weight gain, gastrointestinal disease and limber tail, 2) genetic risks for appetite, limber tail and coat colour changes and 3) factors associated with developing a health microbiome in early life. Uniquely, Dogslife has also quantified the burden of health events which occur in dogs, but which don't result in healthcare (veterinary) presentation. The project has developed novel methodologies and published guidelines for questionnaire design, validation, and big data cleaning, and shared them with the scientific, veterinary and lay communities. The positive experience of the participating dog owners is evident in their long-term commitment to Dogslife. Feedback shows that 98% of participants find contributing to Dogslife a valuable use of their time, 90% were aware of the successes of the project and 88% felt they had contributed to its discoveries.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 77

Applicant details

Submission category: 6 - Community Building

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Tavares, Adriana

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

The “PET is Wonderful” initiative, established in 2015, focused on supporting preclinical positron emission tomography (PET) service provision for the research community at the University of Edinburgh. In just 2 years, the “PET is Wonderful” local team supported over 40 different projects across all colleges of the University. In 2017, the team started a series of “PET is Wonderful” talks for members of the University that covered the latest development in the field of PET imaging and provided a forum for discussion on how that new technology could be used to address critical research questions. The community of PET enthusiasts rapidly propagated beyond the walls of the University and in October 2018, the “PET is Wonderful” conference included speakers from other UK universities, NHS, pharmaceutical companies and contract research organisations. More than 70 delegates attended the 2018 “PET is Wonderful” conference and a similar number participated in the 2019 meeting where speakers from various European and US-based universities gave exciting talks on the latest PET technology. The external “PET is Wonderful” community grew quickly alongside the team of researchers at the University, which expanded again from seven to ten members due to increase in research fund leveraged for PET technology development and pillared on this community activities to promote PET imaging. In 2020, a webpage was launched to serve as an interface for this community (www.petiswonderful.org) and the 2020 conference hosted online counted with >200 delegate registrations. We received very positive feedback from all our conferences and are currently working on organising the 2021 meeting. Furthermore, a free and ever-expanding collection of PET datasets is available for download and re-use by the community (<https://datashare.ed.ac.uk/handle/10283/3219>). Recently funding from the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative (CZI) was secured to support an annual CZI-PET is Wonderful scholarship to train the next generation of imaging scientists.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 107

Applicant details

Submission category: 6 - Community Building

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Furnass, Will

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

LunchBytes is a monthly series of short talks from the research community at the University of Sheffield on research software, data and infrastructure. Historically, the University has had many talks/seminar series centered around research domains but far fewer on the tools and methods that are of value across research domains. Each LunchBytes session is themed and typically comprises three ten-to-fifteen-minute talks plus a Q&A.; Themes have varied greatly, covering topics such as data visualisation tools and techniques, reproducible research and accelerating scientific computing. The branding, the short duration of the talks and timing of events engender an informal atmosphere where interaction and dialogue are welcome. The majority of speakers are from the research community at the University but some speakers have been external. To date there have been six events over eight months, with attendance figures ranging between 30-100 people. From the outset there have been mechanisms for curating Q&A; discussions and for capturing ideas from the community for future themes/speakers/chairs. After each event slides and a video recording are publicly shared via <https://rse.shef.ac.uk/community/lunch-bytes/>, which also contains details of particular sessions. The involvement of the community at all stages of the event, from planning to discussion, makes the events highly interactive. LunchBytes has been popularised through a monthly newsletter, which also features RSE related news, information about software releases, community events and job opportunities. The newsletter has been disseminated within the University, as well as via its own mailing list (~230 members) which is itself promoted further via our LunchBytes talks.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 108

Applicant details

Submission category: 6 - Community Building

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Krystalli, Anna

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Reproducibility has been proposed as a minimum standard for validating research findings and requires that code and data underlying research is published alongside papers. However, the research community currently lacks formal opportunity to practice and hone skills, both in developing open, reproducible research materials and in reviewing and providing feedback on them. ReproHack community events (<https://github.com/reprohack/reprohack-hq>) provide a low pressure sandbox environment for practicing such reproducible research skills! Authors submit their papers, code and data for review while participants at the events attempt reproduction and provide feedback to authors. Authors get to practice producing open, reproducible research materials and receive constructive feedback on their work and, importantly, appreciation of their efforts. Participants have the opportunity to practice reviewing and learn about reproducibility best practice and common pitfalls from real life materials. Importantly they get inspired and grow confidence in working more openly themselves. Overall, the whole research community benefits from the opportunity to evaluate what works best in practice and by developing capacity in reproducible research, of both authors and reviewers, helping to ensure science is not just open, but fit for open purposes. Since the inception of the project, there have been at least 15 events with over 200 participants and ~50 papers submitted for review as well as a vibrant slack community around the project. The event held in Leiden won the Open Initiative Trophy at the Netherlands Open Science Festival and the project has attracted funding from the N8 CIR to build an online hub to support the wider community in running ReproHack events, increasing engagement with the project with the aim of ultimately normalising the process of code review in academia.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 115

Applicant details

Submission category: 6 - Community Building

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Paci, Giulia

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

UCL Bioimage Analysis Interest Group The UCL Bioimage Analysis Interest Group (1) aims to connect users and experts from different backgrounds who are interested in biological and biomedical image analysis in order to foster a community of image analysis aficionados across UCL and beyond. The group was founded 8 months ago by Giulia Paci (Research Fellow) and Alessandro Felder (Research Software Developer) and it has organized virtual monthly meetings hosting two speakers each time (typically early career researchers, including PhD students) for short and informal presentations. The ethos of the group is to foster a constructive and positive atmosphere where speakers are encouraged to present work-in-progress and current issues they face in their image analysis pipeline. The monthly meetings have been regularly attended by approx. 50 participants and have been a great opportunity for researchers to get feedback on their work as well as a platform to share newly developed tools and pipelines with the community. To further build a network of people interested in image analysis across UCL and beyond, the group has also set up a mailing list (150 participants) and a Slack channel (100 participants). The Slack channel in particular has proven to be a great platform for community members to seek advice or advertise relevant events/courses, and it has allowed participants to further engage speakers after their talks with ongoing discussions. Finally, this upcoming June, the group is organizing a collaborative hackday within the context of UCL's festival of code (2) where small groups will work together on a bioimage-analysis-related software project for a day. In line with the spirit of the group, this event is open for participants at all levels and will be a further opportunity of networking and community-building. (1) <https://www.ucl.ac.uk/lmcb/ucl-bioimage-analysis-interest-group> (2) <https://www.ucl.ac.uk/research/domains/eresearch/developing-technical-skills-good-practice-careers/develop-better-research-software-0>

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 125

Applicant details

Submission category: 6 - Community Building

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Powell, Jeff

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

As part of a broader movement to bring greater intra- and inter-disciplinary space ('pluralism') into economics, Reteaching Economics (RE) was established by three academic economists in October 2014, as a network to connect early-career pluralist economists in the UK. It has grown to include over 100 members from over three dozen institutions. RE is a response to the domination of economics by a neoclassical orthodoxy. Adherents control: the way the discipline is taught; hiring and promotion bodies; boards of top journals; research funding decisions in general; and the REF subject panel in particular. The network, driven entirely by volunteer effort, has held twice-annual meetings which have provided spaces for discussion, planning and connection. From these meetings have come a range of initiatives: the creation of a media presence (reteacheconomics.org) which directs prospective students to the pluralist programmes on offer in the UK; two workshops on sharing and promoting best practice in research and education in pluralist economics; an edited volume 'Recharting the History of Economic Thought' (Macmillan, 2020) whose editors/contributors were drawn from the network; support for launches of members' publications; and a space to share pluralist curriculum and teaching materials. While the network has not yet achieved formal organisational status in order to bid for funding, various combinations of members have come together to prepare proposals. Out of such collaborations, several successful applications were made, for example, to the ESRC's Rebuilding Macroeconomics call. In terms of policy influence, the network has provided a space to coordinate a number of public interventions on a range of economic issues, and has led a submission to the consultation on the QAA benchmark statement for economics (which led to an explicit recognition of the value of pluralism in the benchmark statement, opening up space for members to justify their efforts to university administrators.)

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 126

Applicant details

Submission category: 6 - Community Building

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Daley, Christopher

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Engaged Humanities Day, Royal Holloway, University of London (Friday 7th May 2021). This event brought together the British Academy and the School of Humanities at Royal Holloway to explore how engaged/public humanities strategies could align with the British Academy's SHAPE initiative. The day also welcomed speakers from the University of Sussex, King's College London and the V&A; to explore the role of humanities labs as vehicles for dynamic interactions with diverse publics. The event was the first part of network/community building involving researchers, funders, learned societies, schools, community groups and RMA staff with the overall aim of highlighting the broad reach and appeal of arts and humanities research beyond rigid disciplinary and sectoral boundaries. The event was also an opportunity for RMA staff to demonstrate how arts and humanities research has an important role to play in the move towards multi-disciplinary, challenge-focused research and highlighted how arts and humanities researchers can collaborate with academics from all disciplines whilst also being vital for knowledge exchange activities outside academia.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 131

Applicant details

Submission category: 6 - Community Building

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Parsons, Sam

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

I would like to nominate the Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training (FORRT; forrt.org) for its role in community building among educators. The last decade has seen dramatic changes in the process of conducting research. Many of these changes have focused on improving transparency, reproducibility, robustness, and replicability. Despite progress towards the adoption of open scholarship practices across many disciplines, educating researchers and users of research about open and reproducible scholarship has received little attention. However, familiarizing students with the multiple dimensions of open scholarship is crucial to sustaining and developing it in the long run: it enables future generations of scholars to practice open scholarship themselves, helps students as future consumers of research to better understand findings in light of epistemic uncertainty and democratizes open scholarship such that it becomes a more public good, thereby reducing knowledge inequities in academia and beyond. We address the lack of infrastructure for open scholarship education by introducing the Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training (FORRT). FORRT is a community-driven infrastructure for educators that provides them with guidance and resources to aid the inclusion of open and reproducible practices into research training. FORRT encompasses multiple initiatives and tools to facilitate open scholarship training in higher education. In addition to providing a wider ecosystem for resource-sharing and discussion, FORRT offers, among other initiatives, a seven-part roadmap to the open scholarship literature, a curated database of open scholarship materials and teaching pedagogies for customized adoption by teachers, and a self-assessment tool to help educators evaluate the integration of open scholarship tenets in their own teaching and mentoring. Finally, FORRT also is an advocacy community working to sustain principled teaching and mentorship as the fourth pillar of a real scientific utopia.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 143

Applicant details

Submission category: 6 - Community Building

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Cain, Lizzie

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Co-Production Collective is a co-production community where everyone is welcome. We want to see a world where diverse knowledge and experience is recognised and valued in the co-production of research - and beyond. "By being involved in the Collective... I get to work with a diverse range of people to reflect on how to make research more meaningful and impactful." Laura Crane, UCL. Back in 2017, a group got together with an idea: to co-create a centre to support co-production. Funded by the Wellcome Trust and supported by UCL, we were originally known as the UCL Centre for Co-production. Since then, hundreds of co-producers have joined us to co-create everything from our name to our strategy. We launched as Co-Production Collective in October 2020, with 300+ Zoom attendees; we currently have 1,250 newsletter subscribers and 3,000+ Twitter followers. Our membership is national and international; whatever our identity or experience we come together to learn, connect, and champion co-production for lasting change. "This is like therapy for me; it keeps me well." Mark, co-producer. Originally focused on health research, our community now encompasses policy and service delivery across sectors, focusing on amplifying unheard voices. We've secured significant research grant funding and consultancy contracts to continue our work, supporting 4FTE staff. Our activity includes providing resources, networking, and learning platforms, plus our own co-creation sessions. Our co-created training has been co-delivered to research teams, students and charities, while our partnerships range from grassroots groups to funders (NIHR, NHS). "It's a place where skills and knowledge are freely shared and lessons learned from successes and failures are generously communicated." Nick Hillier, Academy of Medical Sciences. Guided by our core values – human, inclusive, transparent and challenging – we're influencing culture change at the top and practice on the ground to create better outcomes for everyone.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 153

Applicant details

Submission category: 6 - Community Building

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Rinke, Eike Mark

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

BUILDING AN OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCE COMMUNITY Eike Mark Rinke has been impactful in building an academic community around making social science more transparent and socially inclusive. He helped expand the discourse of 'Open Science' to the wider social sciences at a time when few social scientists knew how their work was 'closed' and could be 'opened up'. Rinke has since built an Open Social Science community for several years, in multiple roles, and on several levels. On the local level, Rinke delivered workshops on Open Social Science at his respective institutions, the University of Leeds (2019, 2020) and the University of Mannheim (2016). He co-founded the University of Leeds branch of the UK Reproducibility Network (UKRN, 2019) and has since served as its Local Lead. Rinke has built an Open Social Science community at Leeds through contributing to initiatives such as the Leeds Open Research Statement (2020), the Leeds ReproducibiliTea journal club (since 2019), and the 2019/20 Library Annual Report on Open Research. On the discipline level, Rinke has built an Open Social Science community as co-organiser of the first-ever conferences dedicated to the idea of "Open Social Science", the 2019 MZES Open Social Science Conference and the 2020 annual conference of the International Communication Association (ICA) on "Open Communication", with the latter growing out of previous community-building events Rinke had organised at the 2017 and 2019 ICA meetings. Rinke has helped built an Open Social Science community with a focus on training and education as active contributor to initiatives like the Berkeley Initiative for Transparency in the Social Sciences (BITSS), the Project TIER (Teaching Integrity in Empirical Research) Network, and the Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training (FORRT). He has also built community as content moderator at SocArXiv, a community-driven open preprint archive for the social sciences. Nominated by Alex Beresford (Leeds)

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 155

Applicant details

Submission category: 6 - Community Building

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Sena, Emily

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

The University of Edinburgh Race Equality Network (EREN) is for Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic (BAME) colleagues and white allies committed to race equity, diversity and inclusion. EREN was established five years ago by two colleagues, Sena (academic lead) and Creighton-Offord (professional services lead), now has over 100 members and is run by a structured committee (all volunteers) with monthly meetings. We have developed an active community that provides a supportive environment for BAME colleagues, holds the university to account, promotes systemic change and are engaged in anti-racist activism. To improve racial literacy, we have the EREN Book Club open to anyone interested in race equity and anti-racism. We include fiction, non-fiction and academic texts, sessions are well attended and some authors, e.g. Angela Saini, have accepted invitations to participate. To elevate the profile of our BAME researchers, we have the EREN Lunchtime Biography series. These short talks allow members to share their career stories and humanise them to colleagues with different lived experiences. We have also established the Tackling Islamophobia Working Group. The group collaborates with key stakeholders and Edinburgh is on track to be one of the first UK universities to adopt a definition of Islamophobia. Our value is recognised by the institution and we have been invited onto multiple institutional committees and to provide feedback and insights into proposed activities (e.g. the Women of Colour leadership training course/ inclusive language guide around race). We use Twitter and our blog to share our ongoing impact; for example, a white senior research scientist member described how EREN empowered and equipped her to discuss racism in a fellowship funding panel meeting. Our greatest impacts have been ensuring that race equity, diversity and inclusion remain high on our institutional agenda, and nurturing and maintaining a sense of belonging for our BAME community.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 156

Applicant details

Submission category: 4 - Citizen Science

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Ridge, Mia

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

LibCrowds is a platform dedicated to hosting crowdsourcing projects aimed at enhancing access to British Library collections. Since launching in 2015, it has hosted 171 projects, drawing in 265,000 contributions from nearly 3,000 registered volunteers, and many more anonymous individuals. The crowdsourcing projects greatly enhance the discoverability of library collections. Our community of volunteers have contributed to projects such as: 'Georeferencer'—providing more accurate, diverse metadata about digitised historic maps; 'In the Spotlight'—transcribing 18th-19th century playbills (making them more findable and searchable); 'Convert-a-Card'—retro-converting printed card catalogues into electronic records, particularly improving access to Chinese and Indonesian collections. The platform is carefully designed for productivity; it's easy to use and interact with images. However, engagement with collections is also a key outcome. LibCrowds has built a strong community. Our surveys indicate that most contributors participate because it's enjoyable, and some take a personal interest in the subject matter. They can discuss discoveries with others through a forum, and can easily share images via social media. LibCrowds has enabled important research findings. For instance, the playbills project has allowed research on plays which were previously important but which waned in popularity, and has revealed details about marginalised groups including women and Black actors. We are aware of multiple doctoral students working on aspects of theatrical history and researchers in several universities that have used the transcribed collections in their publications. The scholarly and professional literature recognises LibCrowds to be an extremely valuable case study of a successful crowdsourcing project. It's referenced in dozens of articles and conference papers. Recently, insights from LibCrowds have been integral to the planning of research in the Library and Turing Institute's Living with Machines project, using crowdsourcing to engage the public with data science methods and produce effective and timely results about 19th century newspapers.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 161

Applicant details

Submission category: 6 - Community Building

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Konovalov, Alexander

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

I am one of the developers of GAP, an open source system for computational discrete algebra (<https://www.gap-system.org>). Since 2013, I was building the sub-community of GAP users on Mathematics Q&A; site (MSE) of the Stackexchange framework (<https://math.stackexchange.com/tags/gap/info>). This is not the only GAP support channel: we have mailing lists (<https://www.gap-system.org/Contacts/Forum/forum.html>), but they don't have a system to track questions, so either they get instant attention or might never be answered. Issue trackers in <https://github.com/gap-packages> and <https://github.com/gap-system> are more appropriate for development than for the support of users learning GAP. The MSE site, on the other hand, is "a question and answer site for people studying math at any level and professionals in related fields" and its functionality is ideal for this purpose. After seeing some GAP questions answered there by others, I concluded that the lack of GAP developers on MSE impacts the quality of answers, and started to be more active there (see my answers at <https://math.stackexchange.com/users/70316/alexander-konovalov>), also curating questions, promoting them at https://twitter.com/gap_system, informing other GAP developers via Slack, directly contacting people who may answer, or directing the learners to other support channels. What I am particularly proud of today: 624 GAP questions at <https://math.stackexchange.com/questions/tagged/gap?tab=Newest>, with only 12.8% unanswered (to compare, SageMath, another open source maths software, has 273, with 30% unanswered; the overall fraction of unanswered MSE questions is 23%). Alexander Hulpke, one of the key GAP developers, being initially sceptical, now had answered twice more answers than me (<https://math.stackexchange.com/tags/gap/topusers>)! There are only 53 GAP questions at <https://mathoverflow.net/questions/tagged/gap> and 43 at <https://stackoverflow.com/questions/tagged/gap-system> - I am trying to consolidate all GAP questions at MSE which has a critical mass. However, it was not possible to included this in our GAP REF impact case study, since one can't justify this as use of GAP in mathematical education due to the unknown demography of users.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 164

Applicant details

Submission category: 6 - Community Building

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Haley, Jane

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

I'd like to nominate our researchers and all our associated staff for their fantastic embracing of the community building project that has been Edinburgh Neuroscience. Since 2006 Edinburgh Neuroscience has provided a comprehensive package of community building activities which reach a broad range of researchers, students and support staff across the university (>1,500 on our mailing list). The Directors and coordinator have provided a variety of opportunities and activities for the research community, ensuring that researchers at all levels can benefit. From large networking events such as Neuroscience Day (>300 attendees annually) to smaller bespoke events such as the Autumn School for PhD Students and the online 'Beyond a PhD' seminar series, seedcorn funding schemes (RS Macdonald Seedcorn Fund, Neuroresearchers Fund) and public engagement activities (e.g. the current Cajal Embroidery Project). All effectively and efficiently communicated to the entire community via the weekly themed Newsletters. Most importantly, nothing would have changed if it wasn't for the willingness of our community to actively engage and take advantage of these opportunities. To their immense credit, over the past 15 years our researchers have embraced what we have offered and built an incredibly vibrant and collaborative research environment – interdisciplinary working has increased (32% of submitted outputs in REF2021) and funding income have grown as well (2.5-fold increase compared to REF2014). Feedback from the community is really positive: "Throughout my post-doctoral research time, Edinburgh Neuroscience has provided regular opportunities that have helped me to build my cv to the stage where I felt able to apply for fellowship funding. The regular updates on wider funding and learning opportunities have made keeping up to date with relevant grant calls and meetings a lot easier. I'm truly grateful for the support Edinburgh Neuroscience has provided to me" 2021 Wellcome Sir Henry Dale Fellowship Awardee

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 168

Applicant details

Submission category: 6 - Community Building

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Chisholm, Louise

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

The UCL eResearch Domain (eRD), launched June 2016, supports the UCL community who perform research using computational and data sciences or digital technologies. The eRD helps shape the UCL digital infrastructure ecosystem. The steering committee prioritises the UCL's capital investment in research IT and makes recommendations as part of UCL's annual budget cycle. The eRD led the development of the UCL Research Data Strategy and contributed to the Research IT Services' roadmaps (2020-2023). The eRD convenes a monthly forum (since January 2020) bringing together ~20 colleagues from 11 professional and research teams who work at the interface between the researchers and the digital infrastructure ecosystem. The eRD enables researchers to develop their technical skills by supporting and funding grass-roots communities. The UCL Code Club and UCL R User group organise monthly technical seminars or coding challenges. The UCL Data Collaborative brings together researchers (launched April 2020, 60 researchers) who use pharmaco-epidemiology methods and datasets. Each community has their own newsletter and TEAMS site. These initiatives also provide opportunities for early career researchers to develop leadership skills. The eRD enables the community to develop research collaborations. The eRD has organised eight symposia addressing topics ranging from harnessing FAIR data to artificial intelligence. The events are attended by up to 200 researchers and technical professionals, from 70 departments across all 11 faculties. Our monthly newsletter (1292 subscribers) highlights funding and training opportunities. Working with the Research Coordination Offices, the eRD develops strong research proposals. Researchers can book a 1-2-1 sessions to receive feedback on draft proposals with the eRD coordinator. Successes include the EPSRC Tier 2 High Performance Computing Hub in Materials and Molecular Modelling Phase 1 (2016, £4M) and Phase 2 (2019, £4.5M); EPSRC UK AMOR High End Computing Consortia (2018, £360K); UKRI ExCALIBUR: UCL Adaptable Cluster (2020, £400K).

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Communicative outputs panel

Entry: 38

Applicant details

Submission category: H - Website Content

Role submitted: n/a

Name: n/a, n/a

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

www.digitalholocaustmemory.com shares research and provides networking space for individuals and organisations interested in digital Holocaust memory. Its launch in April 2020 was particularly timely as this month saw the commemoration of the 75th anniversaries of the last Nazi concentration camps, events for which were hastily transformed into online provisions. Since the launch, the website has hosted 5 online discussions featuring academics, and Holocaust museum and archive professionals, from the USA, UK, the Netherlands, Denmark, Germany, Poland, Serbia, Israel, South Africa and Australia, each attended by between 65-127 people. It has published a further 20 blog posts, mostly written by its founder and curator Dr. Victoria Grace Walden (University of Sussex) but also including guest posts by PhD students in the UK and Germany. It publishes a crowd-sourced and regularly updated academic reading list on digital Holocaust memory. In late 2020, it also established a Discord server for academics and creatives thinking about Holocaust memory and computer games. The server's moderator team of 10 includes academics and professionals from Germany, the USA, UK and India. In the 8 months since its incarceration, the website has attracted 11,982 views from 6,840 unique visitors from 87 nations. It has 560 people on its mailing list and 64 followers on WordPress or Email. It has 808 Twitter and 477 Facebook followers. The work on the site has led to a number of initiatives: (1) an advisory board for a Holocaust computer game, bringing together museum professionals, educators, academics, a survivor and an LA-based games company. (2) an edited collection and journal special edition together with 30 collaborators. (3) virtual talks for Cape Town Holocaust and Genocide Centre, ITSC, Lille, the University of Oxford, Univeristy of Haifa, Hebrew University, and Falstad Concentration Camp Memorial, Norway, and collaborations with colleagues at Yale and Bergen-Belsen.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 39

Applicant details

Submission category: H - Website Content

Role submitted: n/a

Name: n/a, n/a

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Dr Eoghan Mulholland is a postdoctoral research scientist in cancer genetics at the Wellcome Centre for Human Genetics and a Junior Research Fellow of Somerville College, University of Oxford. In February 2020, Eoghan was appointed to the Communications Committee for the American Society of Gene and Cell therapy (ASGCT). With cross-border collaboration being very important to Eoghan, this has been, and continues to be, a very rewarding position for him in which he works with world-leading scientists from a wide range of backgrounds. Eoghan has produced several engaging educational articles for the ASGCT, across a wide range of topics including the use of gene therapy in the development of vaccines, a highly poignant topic for current times. Other topics have included gene and cell therapies for breast cancer, endometriosis and Parkinson's disease. Eoghan's motivation for these articles is his desire to share science with the general public on topics he feels are valuable, but in an easy-to-understand way. These articles are written in a unique style which is informative, engaging and inspire hope in the future of medicine. Furthermore, Eoghan always talks with researchers from the world over to give input to these articles, this often includes early career researchers which he wants to inspire hope in and give a platform for their voices to be heard. These articles when published are completely open access and are shared extensively online to reach as wide an audience as possible (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, ASGCT website). These articles have received much attention to date, having gathered as much as 1100 unique reads since publication. Also, the average twitter engagement rate for my articles is 3.5%, which is considered excellent for the size of the ASGCT twitter page. (Example piece: <https://bit.ly/2MTSau1>)

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 47

Applicant details

Submission category: L - Physical artefact

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Smyth, Gerry

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

My colleague Dr Andrew Sherlock and I have been involved with the International Flann O'Brien Association since its inauguration at the University of Vienna in 2011. We have contributed original theatrical material to all but one of the bi-annual conferences dedicated to the cult Irish writer, including performances in Prague, Salzburg and Dublin. It was for this latter event in 2019 that we had the idea of collecting ghosted letters written to O'Brien by a range of twentieth-century luminaries. Commencing in October 2019, over the course of the following year we managed to commission 107 letters, written by academics, artists, poets, novelists, politicians, as well as a number of non-academic writers: train drivers, football players, bin men and home-makers. Contributors included three Booker Prize winners, one Pulitzer Prize winner, one Oscar nominee, one Guardian Fiction Prize winner, as well as a number of leaders in their fields - all attracted by the opportunity to enter O'Brien's surreal world. 'The Lost Letters of Flann O'Brien' was published by a small Independent English press in January 2021, and the response thus far has been uniformly positive. The online launch on February 25 was attended by 148 people. With letters from the likes of Walt Disney and Virginia Woolf, Joseph McCarthy and Sylvia Plath (to name only a very few), the book makes for an entertaining yet deceptively challenging read; many leading O'Brien scholars have already admitted that the letters have opened up new and exciting critical possibilities. Not only is the book a truly international project, moreover, with contributors from 23 countries worldwide; it has also been described – by writers and readers alike – as a beacon of hope and cultural positivity during one of the bleakest times in recent history.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 50

Applicant details

Submission category: H - Website Content

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Wilby, David

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

COVID-19 Online Misinformation - The Data Deficits Dashboard <https://datadeficits.firstdraftnews.org/>
The spread of online misinformation is a clear and present threat to the public understanding of global events and public health. Whilst fact checking organisations are fighting the battle to counter misinformation; greater knowledge of where best to place their efforts will aid in making efficient use of their limited resources. During the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, researchers and research software engineers from the GATE research group (<https://gate.ac.uk>) and Research Software Engineering Team (<https://rse.shef.ac.uk>) at The University of Sheffield collaborated with fact-checkers and journalistic researchers at FirstDraft News (<https://firstdraftnews.org/>) to produce a prototype data visualisation dashboard - demonstrating a proof of principle in a new type of analysis in fact checking. By using machine learning based text classifiers combined with up to date social media analytics, we produced data visualisations showing where in the world and for which topics of misinformation that supply of fact-checking was unable to meet public demand - by calculating a quantity called a 'data deficit'. This web app provided a platform for fact checkers to study supply versus demand in fact checking - a new insight for the industry. "Data deficits: why we need to monitor the demand and supply of information in real time" - <https://firstdraftnews.org/long-form-article/data-deficits/> Tommy Shane and Pedro Noel, FirstDraft News

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 55

Applicant details

Submission category: K - Design

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Erolin, Caroline

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

The University of Dundee's D'Arcy Thompson Zoology Museum houses many fascinating specimens from around the world. 2017 saw the centenary of the publication D'Arcy Thompson's celebrated book 'On Growth and Form'. During 2016 I initiated a project to digitise key specimens from the collection as part of the centenary celebrations. Smaller specimens were scanned using a microCT scanner, while larger specimens were captured using hand-held structured light scanners (Artec Eva and Space Spider). The resulting 3D models were further processed using the 3D modelling software Pixologic ZBrush before being hosted online via the 3D viewer Sketchfab (https://sketchfab.com/uod_museums). They are shared under a CC Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike license and are available for use by researchers, educators and the general public alike. To date the Sketchfab site has over 2000 followers with 56 models uploaded to date. Models include scans of bones, skulls, mounted animal skins, insects, fish, and even historical Blaschka glass models. The collection has received over 160,000 views from more than 25 countries, with over 3900 likes and 24000 downloads having taken place. The models are being used in a variety of learning and teaching initiatives including by the University of Queensland in their vertebrate anatomy and evolution module, and the organisation 'Museum in a Box' (<http://museuminabox.org/>). In addition, the project has also led to exchanges with external researchers. For example, we have shared the raw CT data from the Blaschka glass models with researchers in Integrative Biology at University College Dublin to assist in their research surrounding the glass density and other properties. In early 2020, several of the models were changed to a CC0 Public Domain license. These have now been added as an example of good practice by the National Lottery Heritage Fund in their digital guide on working with open licenses (<https://www.heritagefund.org.uk/good-practice-guidance/digital-guide-working-open-licences>).

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 76

Applicant details

Submission category: H - Website Content

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Cohen, Jeremy

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

The Research Software Engineer's Toolkit (RSEToolkit) Background: RSEs and researchers have access to a vast amount of technical information online. However, its unstructured nature makes it difficult to find the right information from the mass of available content. The RSEToolkit summarises important topics and technical material along with providing links to existing content that editors and contributors consider to be helpful. At the 2020 International RSE Leaders Workshop, a small but enthusiastic team came together to redesign a previous template for the RSEToolkit and launch it as an open community resource at <https://rsetoolkit.github.io/>. Content: The RSEToolkit aims to become one of the accepted locations that RSEs go to find reliable, high-quality information to support their work. As a community resource, it has been developed to enable the wider community to add (and edit) content and provide links to existing material. A key initial focus has been providing different entry points to the material based on an individual's role – researcher, new RSE, experienced RSE. Examples are being provided for a set of subject guides, populated by experts in a domain, to provide a high-level overview of a field, key terminology used, common software packages and tools, etc. Alongside this, other material is organised into three top-level areas – Technology, Training and Research. Management: Anyone can contribute content to the RSEToolkit. To prevent the addition of out of scope or duplicate material, maintainers will apply a lightweight review process to check content and approve its inclusion. Community benefit: By making high-quality information more easily accessible and offering content to assist RSEs in moving between domains, the RSEToolkit has the potential to enhance the use of technical best practices, contribute to improving the quality of research software and, ultimately, play a role in improving the overall quality and reproducibility of research outputs.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 80

Applicant details

Submission category: N - Research report for external body

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Lundie, David

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

<http://cepa.hope.ac.uk/media/microsites/cepa/documents/SecuritySafeguardingandtheCurriculum.pdf>

The 'Security, Safeguarding and the Curriculum' report was the result of a British Academy funded project exploring the implementation of the 'Prevent' counter-terrorism duty in schools at its inception. Its rigour comes from in-depth interviews tracing the professional networks involved in training school leaders and teachers about their duties under Prevent, including those working outside of traditional institutions in the private and 3rd sector. Following this, a 2-day multi-professional conference was held to discuss the findings, making use of the Delphi method, resulting in this publication. The study found that policy interpretations were widely divergent, and depended on professional histories and values.

This led to two distinct understandings of Prevent - either as primarily a referral process, or as a curriculum matter, having a bearing on the civic, social and moral education of young people.

Professional consensus, working with subject associations for Citizenship, RE and PSHE, settled on the advantages of the latter approach, resulting in the recommendations in this report. Following the publication of this report, Prevent Education Officers were funded by the Home Office, located in the Department of Education and serving in Local Authorities in high priority Prevent areas. These individuals bridged the two clashing institutional understandings of Prevent which were identified in the report.

Although it is impossible to evidence the link between the report and policy change, Home Office personnel were involved in the interviews and conference, and signalled an interest in the findings. (For those not familiar with the world of counter-terrorism, Home Office includes both those on civil service contracts and those working for the Security Service, MI5, who would not identify themselves as such to a researcher.)

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 82

Applicant details

Submission category: Q - Digital or Visual Media

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Carder, Gemma

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Brooke is an international charity that protects and improves the lives of working horses, donkeys and mules, as well as the people who depend on them for their livelihoods. Research is a vital part of Brooke's work, informing both our programming and advocacy. It also provides us with an increased understanding of the issues working equids and their owners face. As an INGO that conducts ethical and applied research, we believe we have a responsibility to share our research so that a wide range of audiences can easily understand it and use it. To help us do this, in 2020 we launched our first annual Research Review. The report showcased the research that Brooke does in house and in partnership and shared key findings and lessons learned during 2019. The report was hugely successful. It was shared widely on social media and was praised for being a visually appealing and informative way of raising the issues that working equids and their owners face. Based on the success of the first research review, we launched our second one in April 2021. Key studies highlighted in the review include a study on the welfare of coal mine workers and their donkeys in Pakistan and research on the socio economic contributions of donkeys to communities in Burkina Faso. Our second Research Review has received fantastic feedback for the use of impactful imagery and easily digestible case studies that appeal to a range of audiences. The Review also achieved excellent levels of engagement across social media; gaining an 11.37% click rate for the paid promotion, and was in the top 10 best performing organic Tweets posted by Brooke from February – mid April. We believe that our Research Review serves as an innovative, informative and visually appealing research report that raises the profile of research at Brooke.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 89

Applicant details

Submission category: H - Website Content

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Tuppen, Sandra

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

The British Library's Heritage Made Digital Programme (HMD) digitises rare and unique collection items and makes them freely available online for everyone to study, enjoy and use in their research. Over the last two years, HMD has worked with the Library's curators to digitise Tudor and early Stuart manuscripts. These early modern manuscripts have become some of the Library's most popular content online. Social media has allowed a wider audience of researchers and potential researchers to engage directly with historic materials. The early modern manuscript project has digitised 600 manuscripts using high-resolution photography. This material includes letters from the royal family - including Elizabeth I, Charles I and James I - state papers, and other historical documents, literary works and scientific texts. Three specialist cataloguers with expertise in Tudor and Stuart history were recruited to re-catalogue the manuscripts, which was originally catalogued in the nineteenth century. The material now has far more accessible and detailed catalogue records. This is discoverable and searchable via the British Library's online catalogue (<https://searcharchives.bl.uk>) and the Digitised Manuscripts platform (<https://www.bl.uk/manuscripts>). The cataloguers made many important new discoveries, and identified the authors of hitherto anonymous material. They included detailed bibliographies in their catalogue records, enabling students and scholars to locate relevant material. A series of blog posts has been written to widely promote the content, which have been viewed by a large international audience. It has also been promoted via social media, where it has been very positively received. The Medieval Manuscripts Blog, which hosts the blog content, receives in excess of 500,000 views per year and the Twitter account generates millions of monthly impressions. Qualitative feedback has also been received from researchers highlighting how useful it is to have online access, especially during the pandemic when the Library buildings have been closed for long periods.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 122

Applicant details

Submission category: Q - Digital or Visual Media

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Priego, Ernesto

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

(Apologies if received duplicated- realised form corrected my email incorrectly!) According to the Royal National Institute for the Blind (RNIB), more than two million people have sight loss and about 350,000 people are registered blind or partially sighted in the UK (RNIB 2019). Information about social distancing measures in the UK has been mainly visual and therefore poses specific challenges for visually impaired persons. We co-designed a COVID-19 rapid response two-page comic created employing user-centred methods adapting an interview with a visually impaired person and their experience of the communication of social distancing measures during the early stages of the first COVID-19 pandemic UK lockdown between March and April 2020. The comic is titled "Community Matters: Please Be Kind". In the spirit of open access and open science, the comic was licensed with a Creative Commons Attribution license. Deposited on figshare, the comic is "in the top 5% of all research outputs scored by Altmetric. The development of the comic was motivated by the creative brief from the United Nations, particularly addressing the 'Key Message' of 'kindness contagion', which was to have the 'tone: common humanity, mental health, caring, solidarity, empowerment, destigmatisation, inclusive, joy' (United Nations 2020) as well as the RNIB's #InfoForAll campaign (RNIB 2020). In co-designing this rapid response comic with a visually impaired co-designer and co-author the team recognised it was working 'with asymmetry', rather than attempting symmetry (Bennett and Rosner 2019). Ethical guidelines were followed and written co-design and co-authorship consent was signed by the three co-authors of the comic. Priego, Ernesto; de la Mora, Francisco; Huddy, Hugh (2020): Community Matters: Please Be Kind. (A COVID-19 Response Comic). City, University of London. Poster. <https://doi.org/10.25383/city.12357215.v1>

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 123

Applicant details

Submission category: Q - Digital or Visual Media

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Priego, Ernesto

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

(Once again apologies if received duplicated- I may have included an incorrect email suggested by the form by accident). By 2030, 82 million people are anticipated to have dementia and 152 million by 2050. Parables of Care is an international collaborative project that explores the potential of co-designed comics to enhance the impact of dementia care research. We have openly shared online two comics developed using user-centred design and narrative research design methods: Parables of Care: Creative Responses to Dementia Care (2017) and I Know How This Ends: Stories of Dementia Care (2020). In the first volume employed the form of the parable to tell individual stories based in real-life cases as told by carers. The second volume shows the importance of feeling in care-giving, the professional aspects of which are sometimes at odds with the family systems aspect of dementia. Both comics can be downloaded as PDF files, under a Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International License, from <http://openaccess.city.ac.uk/18245/> and <https://openaccess.city.ac.uk/id/eprint/23705>. Both comics are also available for free on print and more than 200 print copies have been requested by librarians, researchers, health professionals and members of the public. The first volume is also available on Spanish and German translations. With this project we aim to continue making a contribution to widen the dissemination of one of the key challenges of our time. Find more about the project, its recent activities and some of the reader feedback at <https://blogs.city.ac.uk/parablesofcare/readers-on-parables-of-care/>

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 127

Applicant details

Submission category: N - Research report for external body

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Daley, Christopher

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Authors: Rapple, C (Kudos Innovations); Daley, C (Royal Holloway); Armstrong, D (TBI Communications). Title: Brave New World: Scholarly Communication After COVID. Date: March 2021. Abstract: The coronavirus pandemic has both disrupted research, and acted as a catalyst for change. Publishers, societies and providers of related services urgently need intelligence and analysis to inform short-term responses and longer-term planning. This study, carried out between November 2020 and February 2021, provides up-to-the-minute insight drawn from two global surveys (with responses from 10,000+ researchers and 600+ librarians) and a review of over 100 announcements, articles and other relevant documents from funders, institutions and researchers. Expert analysis highlights the key implications, identifies the emerging opportunities, and sets out clear recommendations for putting the report's findings into practice. Additional Information: This report was a collaboration between Kudos Innovations, TBI Communications and Christopher Daley (Royal Holloway, University of London) to provide scholarly publishers and learned societies with insights into the impact of the coronavirus pandemic on a range of scholarly practices. The report was sponsored by Kudos Innovations, Cactus Communications, Royal Society of Chemistry, STM, Wiley, The American Chemical Society (ACS), American Society of Microbiology (ASM), BMJ, and Karger Publishers. URL: <https://info.growkudos.com/brave-new-world-report>

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 141

Applicant details

Submission category: M - Exhibition

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Breay, Claire

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

The British Library's 2018 exhibition, 'Anglo-Saxon Kingdoms: Art, Word War', was the first national exhibition on Anglo-Saxon England since 1991. Close collaboration with seven academic advisers and an embedded doctoral student shaped the exhibition and integrated new research within it. It also delivered exceptional levels of public engagement. The exhibition featured outstanding manuscripts from the Library's collection and loans from 24 national and international institutions, including recent archaeological finds, such as objects from the Staffordshire Hoard. The exhibition approached the Anglo-Saxon kingdoms in the context of their broader European connections, showing the sophistication of their craftsmanship, literary culture and political organisation. Hosting a doctoral student (Rebecca Lawton), collaborating in a related research network project, and working very closely with academic specialists created strong academic collaboration around the exhibition. This collaboration supported the development of the exhibit list and the exhibition catalogue which sold over 16,000 copies and won the International Society for the Study of Early Medieval England's 'Best Research Aid' publication prize. A three-day conference with leading specialists was hosted in December 2018, and an edited volume of 14 conference papers was published in 2021. The exhibition generated 112 pieces of media coverage: 69 online, 17 broadcast and 26 in print, including five-star reviews in the Guardian and Evening Standard. 108,268 visitors attended, with evaluation revealing an exceptional visitor enjoyment rating of 9.2/10, and visitor dwell-time was very long, averaging 2 hours 50 minutes. It also achieved broad reach: 27% of visitors came from London, 54% from elsewhere in the UK and 19% from overseas. 11% of the visitors were from social grades C2DE. Visitor responses included: 'We actually came to London [from Luxembourg] with this as our main purpose.'; 'I just thought it was amazing... the illuminated manuscripts I just think are stunning ...'; 'Just overwhelming brilliant.'

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 68

Applicant details

Submission category: I - Performance

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Swijghuisen Reigersberg, Muriel

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

The Printer.... Research identities are performed. They are a product of what society thinks they ought to be, and therefore come to be...a bit like Goffman (1956) says they will, unless someone, somewhere, sparks and ignites the desire for a significant change, from within. And not just locally. But Globally. With a CAPITAL 'G'. Research is a Global industry (and 'yes' sorry purists, research in many places is an 'industry' despite aversions to the term....and since when have aversions gotten us anywhere, apart from opinion pieces in (usually) the Guardian?). The Printer tells the story of co-authorship with African researchers, writing, performance, religiosity and internet privileges. The Printer.... Music. It's performance based and yet we must produce written materials to somehow justify investment and continuity in our area of research. Music departments are being shut down, staff made redundant the world over (Monash (Australia), Keele (UK), to name but a few). Never mind the REF...vague definitions of 'excellence' are abundant everywhere. South Africa is developing its own 'Excellence exercise' as we speak, is what my colleagues in Johannesburg, Witwatersrand tell me. Excellence is 'English-writing' and 'near-native speaking'. Not musicking (Small, 1998) and especially not in South Africa. Excellence is written and not experienced, even if recordings, compositions, and art works are permissible. Excellence is privilege: poorer countries without access to English and education cannot participate fully in the global production and dissemination of new knowledge equally, thereby influencing rankings. Co-authors from other parts of the world are not acknowledged as they should be. Co-authorship and editorship in HASS subjects are undervalued. Long-live the solo-authored monograph, the printed word, academic secularist trends, knowledge colonialism, access to the internet and online articles. Never mind the Hidden REF. Let's uncover the REF that never was and may never be, unless we collectively change.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 144

Applicant details

Submission category: I - Performance

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Crudgington, Bentley

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

My work bridges publics, patient, community and stakeholder engagement and links research, policy and practice. My role, as creative facilitator, has been to address the culture of communication around animal research and reimagine who could inform these discussions and how it might feel to participate. By diversifying and investing in the culture of communication, the sector can get a deeper and more nuanced understanding of societal concerns and begin work to collectively address them. My practice combines participation, performance, post-humanism and feminist care theories with methodologies used by the researchers; including history, sociology, cultural geography, and anthropology. My work makes visible other labour that is also underrepresented in the REF, such as those of technicians, patients, lay people and advisory ethics bodies. By centring care and ethics, I help people have difficult and normally private conversations publicly. I prioritise the participant as I am passionate about democratising engagement and involvement across the lifetime of biomedical research. I am deeply invested in looking at societal sentience and the social contracts that both support and give permission for biomedical research while also making them matters of concern. My facilitation work varies from large scale immersive theatre to intimate one-on-one discussions between two people. These activities differ in form and methods, but they foreground the conversation as the unit of exchange. Current examples include (<https://animalresearchnexus.org/public-engagement>): Vector - An immersive theatre experience that tasks participants with ethically reviewing the use of animal models in vaccine development. First toured in 2019. Mouse Exchange - A crafty curiosity-driven activity that creates a space for participants to relate to laboratory mice differently. Psychic Fish - How you really feel about fish! An interactive encounter that invites people to think about fish and their use in research (used internationally). The Work - Are research animals an invisible workforce within a city? Touring Installation

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 91

Applicant details

Submission category: H - Website Content

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Cohen, Jeremy

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Working with software and data at Imperial College London Overview: A set of web content “Working with Software and Data at Imperial College London” (<https://www.imperial.ac.uk/computational-methods/software-data/>) has been developed to offer researchers and academics a common access point to a collection of important information about software and data practices and policies from across the institution. Background: A large academic institution such as Imperial has various teams supporting aspects of research data management, high performance computing, open access and related areas. The vast array of information available in these fast-changing areas, combined with differences between domains in both approaches and training, can sometimes make it challenging for researchers to know where to start when looking for information relating to research software and research data. To help support researchers working with software and data, Jeremy Cohen (RSE), Katerina Michalickova (Training) and Wayne Peters (Research Data Management) have created a set of web content to provide a resource for members of the Imperial research community. Details: The web content brings together links to a series of resources from across Imperial's website and beyond. Grouped into sections – Data, Software, Best practices, RSE resources and External resources – the material provides a brief overview for the different areas, highlighting some key points and practices. It then provides links to wide array of existing material within the institution that can help researchers to answer their questions, address challenges and follow recommended approaches. Benefits: Imperial has more than 3,500 research and academic staff and a similar number of full-time postgraduate research students. The information being provided offers the potential to help enhance the quality of research outputs produced by researchers working with software and data, ensuring that they are aware of and know where to access information on best practices, recommended tooling and processes.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 92

Applicant details

Submission category: H - Website Content

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Hodge, Daryl

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

<https://covid19-druginteractions.org> COVID-19 Drug Interactions is an interactive website written by the Liverpool Drug Interactions group, based at the University of Liverpool, together with collaborators in Basel, Glasgow, and Radboud. The website was developed in March 2020 in response to the great clinical need of the emerging COVID-19 pandemic. Patients with severe COVID-19 are often those with underlying health conditions, putting them at risk of drug interactions. The website summarizes the potential for interaction between COVID-19 drugs and likely comedications. Each interaction is assessed for risk by a panel of experts including clinical pharmacists and an infectious diseases consultant and is given a grade using a 'traffic-light' system. Users select a COVID-19 agent and comedication, and the colour of the returned interaction indicates the recommended course of action – green to proceed, yellow proceed with advice, amber use with caution, and red do not proceed. We have reached over 22,000 unique monthly users from 218 countries and territories since launch. The website has also been cited in 20 clinical treatment guidelines worldwide. Outside of the interactive checker, users can download printable drug interaction charts, useful in areas with limited internet access, along with other prescribing resources, such as our popular PDF on administering agents to intubated patients and dose modification guides for patients with renal or hepatic impairment. Our belief is that drug information should be free of charge, independent, evidence-based, and transparent. Our website is freely available, of crucial importance given the unequal impact of the pandemic worldwide. We are responsive to our users, polling for requests for required medications, and the expert panel meets once a month to keep us up to date with the current situation. We have published our methodology behind the website, and our assessment of risk for each COVID-19 drug is available on the website.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 121

Applicant details

Submission category: H - Website Content

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Priego, Ernesto

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

(Sincere apologies if received duplicated- in case of email error). The Comics Grid: Journal of Comics Scholarship is a researcher-led, open-access (OA), peer-reviewed academic journal which aims to advance the media-specific study of graphic narrative from multidisciplinary perspectives. It promotes comics scholarship within academia and the general public with contributions that present specialised knowledge in accessible forms. As a website we encourage digital research, data sharing, public engagement and collaboration. In January 2021 the journal celebrated a decade as a publication. Starting as a 'peer-edited' blog, by our third year the journal had launched as a full-fledged OA journal. In 2016 the Open Library of Humanities took the journal under its wing, and since then a purely volunteer researcher-led team has reviewed, copyedited, published and disseminated 104 articles, with no APCs charged to authors. According to Altmetric, The Comics Grid is the most mentioned journal of all comics studies journals tracked by the service. On Twitter and Facebook we have a dedicated and engaged audience of more than 7000 followers, and organise an ongoing series of free research webinars. The journal pioneered Creative Commons licenses in the arts and humanities at a time when dominant scholarly cultures strongly resisted them. The Comics Grid advocated OA before it was mandated by our governments and institutions; we embraced it as a precondition and advocated it from the start (We launched in 2011; the UKRI Policy on OA came into force until 1 April 2013). The Comics Grid has shown scholarly publishing is something academics could do ourselves without the mediation of for-profit third parties. The journal continues true to its first reason for existence, which is providing immediate OA on the principle that making research freely available to the public supports a greater global exchange of knowledge. Find us at <https://www.comicsgrid.com/>

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 138

Applicant details

Submission category: H - Website Content

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Macpherson, Fiona

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Extreme Imagination Exhibition <https://www.gla.ac.uk/imagination> A small percentage of the population do not experience mental imagery (they have aphantasia); another minority experience particularly vivid imagery (they have hyperphantasia). Both groups include artists, writers, and designers. The Extreme Imagination Exhibition presents their work, inviting us to consider the role of mental imagery in making art. How can someone make anything without being able to imagine what they want it to look like? Is there a distinctly hyperphantasic kind of art? We believe this is the first exhibition to reflect on these questions—because the centrality of mental imagery to art-making has previously been assumed. This online exhibition is the digital counterpart of twin exhibitions hosted by Tramway, Glasgow, and the Royal Albert Memorial Museum, Exeter, in 2019—together with the essays from the exhibition catalogue from the Eye's Mind researchers, artist interviews, videos of talks at the concurrent conference, and resources about extremes of imagery. It includes the Vividness of Visual Imagery Questionnaire allowing people to gauge their own imagery and feedback forms, which the researchers can gather data from. The images on the website are captioned for the use of screen readers and the artist interviews are subtitled. Effective public engagement, including this website, prompted over 14,000 people with extreme imagery to contact the Eye's Mind researchers. They often reported a prior awareness that something was different about themselves, that they struggled to explain. The research allowed them to understand how they differed from others; and point to the research to verify and explain this difference to others. The Eye's Mind team: Adam Zeman (neurology), Fiona Macpherson (philosophy), John Onions (art history), Crawford Winlove (neuroscience), Susan Aldworth (artist) and Matthew MacKisack (English). The physical exhibitions were curated by Aldworth and MacKisack. Macpherson and Joanna Helfer conceived and created the online version.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 139

Applicant details

Submission category: H - Website Content

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Macpherson, Fiona

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

The Illusions Index <https://www.illusionsindex.org/> Our senses are remarkable. They have evolved to enable us to accurately perceive a huge variety of things in different conditions. However, occasionally our senses let us down, and we fail to perceive the world accurately. The resulting illusions give us great insight into how our senses work, and how they usually manage to do so astonishingly well. Illusions intrigue us. It is fascinating to observe our senses getting things wrong, even when we know the nature of the illusion. The Illusions Index enhances this experience by exhibiting beautiful examples, allowing people to manipulate and test their senses, explaining why illusions occur, and provoking philosophical thoughts about the nature of perception and reality. What are we aware of when we seem to be aware of something that isn't there in the world in front of us? The Illusions Index is a fully searchable, interactive, curated collection of illusions by researchers at the Centre for the Study of Perceptual Experience, University of Glasgow. The illusions are categorised into different types, allowing you to compare illusions of the same kind. It is an open-access resource, primarily intended for use by the general public and, secondarily, for philosophy and psychology researchers. The pages for each illusion are stable URLs, allowing researchers to easily cite illusions in scholarly work using them. The Illusions Index was conceived of by Professor Fiona Macpherson and designed together with Dr Keith Wilson and web-design company Mucky Puddle in 2017. Many graduate students have come to gain experience of communicating with the public by writing for the site. In 2019, we added the Master of Illusions Quiz to the website which tests your knowledge of illusions in a game-style format. Successful completion of all four levels allows people to earn a 'Master of Illusion' certificate.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 142

Applicant details

Submission category: H - Website Content

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Butterworth, Jody

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

The British Library's Endangered Archives Programme (EAP) funds cultural heritage preservation projects and makes enormous amounts of digital material available to a wide online audience. The project has grown since 2004, funding over 405 projects in 90 countries; 80 projects are active as of 2021. Grants are provided to digitise and document archives at risk of loss or decay, and EAP enhances local capabilities for managing and preserving collections. Copies of digitised material are hosted by the British Library and made available through the EAP website (<https://eap.bl.uk>). This currently amounts to 9,000,000 images and 25,000 soundtracks. Metadata is ingested, corrected, enhanced and made available via the EAP website, resulting in collections being accessible to researchers, and for public education and enjoyment. The website has accrued over 4,000,000 unique page views, with the vast majority (>85%) coming from outside the UK, including India, Peru, Indonesia, Ethiopia and Bulgaria. Archive material is often featured in BL exhibitions to widen public engagement with international cultural heritage, most recently in the Buddhism exhibition. Numerous conference papers and published articles have shown the importance of the EAP material to scholars worldwide. SOAS academics most recently demonstrated that EAP collections changed views about Islamic manuscripts in Southeast Asia, since previous research was primarily based on European colonial collections. EAP staff actively look to make the website more inclusive and accessible. Intellectual property rights are respected, as high resolution images are not distributed directly through the website, which instead refers requests to the archival material owners. EAP has also addressed colonial terms in cataloguing schema. Crowdsourcing platforms have been utilised to obtain more specialist and relevant terms from communities. Since 2018, all the images available on the EAP website are IIIF compliant, and ways to make the database more interrogable through data science methods are being researched.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 167

Applicant details

Submission category: H - Website Content

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Welford, Mark

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

The Fuse Open Science Blog (<https://fuseopenscienceblog.blogspot.com>) offers a unique and exciting insight into the world of public health research. Health affects us all and our posts are about issues that have a real-life impact on people. Public health is a broad-discipline and the strength of the blog is in the breadth of our writers and the topics we cover. The blog offers a behind the scenes look at what academics and researchers get up to. Also publishing posts from people working at the 'coalface' in the NHS, local authorities and voluntary organisations. We challenge our contributors to write in an accessible, entertaining and engaging way with a non-specialist audience in mind. Blog posts cover major public health concerns like obesity, physical activity, alcohol, smoking and of course COVID-19 but also factors that affect people's health throughout their lives - from pregnancy to end of life - such as austerity, welfare, housing, cancer and mental health. In more than 540 eclectic posts you can read about junk food advertising, diversity in research, imposter syndrome, inequalities and inactivity, getting research into practice, patient and public involvement, knowledge exchange, embedded research, impact, giving evidence to parliament, Universal Credit, surviving lockdown, the digital divide, food banks, working from home, retirement, reaching the 'hard to reach', diabetes and rugby, survival sex, stress, work-life balance, managing difficult conversations, fish and chips, and the mystery of the humble crisp. The blog posts often spark discussion on social media (#fuseblog) or in the comments section on the platform. We hope that the blog entertains, informs and engages readers about the realities of public health research, can promote interest and collaboration across our readership and, ask difficult questions like: can cancer ever be a good thing, and why do some women continue to smoke when they are pregnant?

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Applications of Research panel

Entry: 49

Applicant details

Submission category: S - Research Datasets and Databases

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Davies, Jamie

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

The Guide to Pharmacology database: <https://www.guidetopharmacology.org/> This database, run from University of Edinburgh, was created to promulgate standard pharmacological nomenclature from the Nomenclature Committee of the International Union of Basic and Clinical Pharmacology (NC-IUPHAR). Over the last decade it has grown to be far more than that, listing quantitative pharmacological information on human drug targets and on around 10,000 ligands (drugs etc.), providing seamless links to databases of chemistry, molecular structure and disease, and custom interfaces for special communities. In particular, at the beginning of 2020, it launched a new section for COVID-19 pharmacology, intensely used during the 'dash for drugs' period of the pandemic. Though run on a shoe-string, currently with financial support from the British Society of Pharmacology and the Medicines for Malaria Venture, and in-kind support from the University itself and IUPHAR, the Guide to Pharmacology resource has 29,000 users per month and 43,000 use sessions. A proportion of these are from the Global South, where access to high quality medical information can be difficult. Academic rigour is ensured by expert human curation, aided by specialist peer review committees from IUPHAR (more than 500 people in total, all of whom give their time voluntarily). A measure of how the resource is trusted is given by the way that major global resources such as NCBI link to us for information (12% of our users arrive via links from NCBI), Pubchem has reciprocal links to us, and publishers such as Wiley embed as standard, hyperlinks to our database in all papers published in certain of their journals to provide information to readers about drugs and targets mentioned in those papers. The database, though it does not fit classical REF outputs, is a major part of the pharmacology research landscape.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 67

Applicant details

Submission category: G - Software

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Cohen, Jeremy

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

django-drf-filepond: filepond file upload in Django web applications Overview: django-drf-filepond (<https://github.com/ImperialCollegeLondon/django-drf-filepond>) is an open source software library for use in Python's Django web framework. Django is a widely used framework for building web applications in both commercial and research environments. Django-drf-filepond integrates into Django applications to handle files uploaded via the widely used filepond (<https://github.com/pqina/filepond>) client-side file upload library. It offers support for the full filepond API and also includes the ability to store uploaded files on remote cloud-based storage services such as Amazon S3. Significance: django-drf-filepond provides an example of the wide-ranging contribution that the work of RSEs can have. It was developed as part of a prototype for a large research software pipeline. However, its general nature, supporting files uploaded through filepond, made it a strong candidate to be packaged and released as a library in its own right. The library has applicability to a huge range of web applications that may be developed for both research and commercial applications. It demonstrates how RSEs' work can provide extensive benefits and contributions beyond their core target domain. Development and availability: The initial prototype of django-drf-filepond underwent additional work to provide a comprehensive test suite, to package it according to Python packaging standards, set up continuous integration and write extensive documentation and a tutorial. It provides a good demonstration of many of the best practices that RSEs are taught to apply as part of their development work. First released 2.5 years ago, the library is available via PyPi (<https://pypi.org/project/django-drf-filepond/>) and can be installed by developers directly from their command line using the pip package manager. Documentation is provided on "Read the Docs" (<https://django-drf-filepond.readthedocs.io/>). Statistics: At the time of writing, django-drf-filepond has been downloaded more than 44,000 times from PyPi (source: <https://pepy.tech/project/django-drf-filepond>) and received 50 stars on GitHub.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 75

Applicant details

Submission category: G - Software

Role submitted: n/a

Name: DeBruine, Lisa

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

I am submitting the open-source R package “faux” for the Software category (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2669586>). This software makes it straightforward to simulate data with factorial designs by specifying the within and between-subjects factor structure, each cell mean and standard deviation, and correlations between cells where appropriate. This can be used to create simulated data sets to be used in preparing the analysis code for pre-registration or registered reports. It can also be used to create data sets for simulation-based power analyses. In addition, it can be used to teach statistical concepts or produce data sets for teaching. Thus, it contributes to the success of research by facilitating open science practices such as pre-registration and registered reports, facilitating robust research planning, and training researchers in statistical concepts. I have been developing faux since 2018 as an extension of my own research and teaching, and made it available to the public starting early 2019. Since it was accepted by the Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN) in August 2020, the package has been downloaded more than 6200 times. (Unfortunately, I do not have access to download statistics from GitHub.) As well as providing extensive online tutorials (<https://debruine.github.io/faux/>), I have also taught workshops on data simulation using faux to early career researchers at the UKRI Advanced Methods Workshop, Radboud University in Nijmegen, University of Grenoble in France, and at the upcoming PsyPAG Data Simulation Summer School (<https://simsummerschool.github.io/>).

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 81

Applicant details

Submission category: S - Research Datasets and Databases

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Roscoe, Katy

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

My submission is a database of 2583 prisoners incarcerated on Cockatoo Island, a colonial-era prison island in Sydney Harbour (<https://cockatooconvicts.wordpress.com/database/>). It was transcribed manually from archival materials held by State Archives of NSW solely by Katy Roscoe (University of Liverpool). It is freely available for download as an excel document, with one line for each convict tracing their journey in and out of custody in the Australian colony. It was created for family historians to trace criminal ancestors, as access to digital resources of this type are paywalled by genealogical websites and most free-to-use digital projects focus on convict-era which stopped to New South Wales in 1840 (my database covers period 1847-69). The database is ideal for tracing criminal ancestors because it includes personal details (name, ship of arrival, age, religion, place of birth, trade), and biometric information (eye/hair colour, complexion, tattoos, scars). It is also a useful longitudinal criminological study and resource freely available to researchers in history and criminology. It has over-turned long-standing myths about Cockatoo Island prisoners as violent recidivists, by showing that 54% were convicted of non-violent property crimes and less than 10% for violent crimes. The prison island is remembered, thanks to its UNESCO world heritage status as convict site, for being a secondary punishment station for transported convicts who couldn't rehabilitate into colonial society in Australia. Yet, this database has shown an equal number of inmates were free immigrants or born in the colony. This shifts focus towards diversity of prisoners, identifying 37 Chinese, 21 Aboriginal and 14 Afro-Caribbean or Indian prisoners on the island. I included blogposts to showcase experiences of these cohorts of prisoners in my "convict lives" section of the website. The website has had 934 visitors, mostly from the UK, Australia and the USA since launch in February 2020 up till April 2021.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 84

Applicant details

Submission category: S - Research Datasets and Databases

Role submitted: n/a

Name: van Blerk, Lorraine

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Growing up on the Streets is a longitudinal qualitative data set co-produced with street children and youth in three African cities: Accra (Ghana), Bukavu (DRC), and Harare (Zimbabwe). Consisting of 2,478 qualitative data files (over 7 million words and 10,000 pages), this large data set is the result of collaboration between street youth who acted as street researchers, UK academics and practitioners, and street workers in the three cities. Each file is a unique street ethnography created by street youth about their own lived experiences and peers in their social networks. Every week for a period of three years, six street researchers in each city (18 in total) recounted their ethnographic narrative reports to a trusted street worker. Ethnographic reports were framed by a capability approach, made up of ten capabilities that street children and youth established as part of the research design. All reports were recorded, transcribed into English by local translators, and sent to the University of Dundee where data was cleaned and anonymised. The full data set has been placed in ReShare at the UK Data Service, freely accessible to others for in-depth analysis. This vital and extensive record provides a unique insight into the lives of street children and youth in African cities. Data is grouped by researcher chronologically so that individual stories can be tracked across years, enabling researchers to engage in longitudinal analysis of individuals or collectively across a variety of themes, including broad issues affecting street children and youth (health, shelter, the role of gender) to specific research interests. The data has been made available with the intention that the aims of Growing up on the Streets – to change the political and social discourses around street children and youth, humanise their experiences and give them a voice – can be achieved.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 87

Applicant details

Submission category: S - Research Datasets and Databases

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Gould, Sara

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

The British Library's EThOS e-thesis service provides an entry point to the wealth of UK doctoral research. The service maintains, and makes openly available, comprehensive bibliographic metadata on over 575,000 doctoral theses. It also provides access to full-text for over 250,000 records. EThOS has enhanced the visibility of valuable doctoral research and enabled opportunities for additional research. Despite some six million pages of doctoral research being produced annually, it usually remains unpublished and underused. However, the research contained within theses is cutting-edge and extremely detailed. EThOS harvests metadata from all UK universities, which is normalised to produce an accurate, validated and trusted dataset. In addition to providing easy access to doctoral research, the dataset has enormous research value in its own right. A regularly updated snapshot of the entire dataset is available under a CC-BY licence. Tens of thousands have made use of individual theses in their research, and a growing number of researchers have used the dataset for innovative studies. A recent acknowledgement stated, "Their [EThOS] meticulous curation of digital doctoral theses has made this work possible". In 2016, chemists discovered 47,000 compounds described in UK theses, of which 50% were new, had not been described elsewhere, and were assessed to be of high value to external drug discovery teams. In another example, a group of WikiData scientists produced a Wikipedia citation structure. Theses listed in Wikipedia subject bibliographies are now among the most heavily-downloaded. Planned research includes a project to assess how research institutions beyond higher education (e.g. charities, heritage organisations) can more easily reuse doctoral research. EThOS is recognised as a vital component of the global open access infrastructure. It continues to evolve to better enable text mining and dataset reuse, and works with UK universities to advance the movement towards the openly available full-text of theses.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 103

Applicant details

Submission category: G - Software

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Matthews, Adam

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Lancsbox software produced by the great Corpus Linguistics team at Lancaster University has really helped me publish, complete my PhD and to learn how to use corpus linguistics as a method and methodology. The software has lots of guides and support from both a technical and user perspective but also backed up by a team of internationally renowned academics in the field. The annual conference and other events form a good community around the software too. I am not a linguist but the field of corpus linguistics really interested me and the resources and publicly available software have helped me to take on the research method and use it in a more sociological manner.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 105

Applicant details

Submission category: P - Devices and Products

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Reddyhoff, Dennis

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

AirQo is a SME (Small Medium Enterprise) that has been spun out of research collaborations between Makerere and Sheffield universities. The project aims to use a network of low-cost sensors across Kampala, Uganda to monitor air quality levels and provide accurate and accessible data to citizens and other NGO's in order to provide empirical data to use as part of campaigns to improve air quality in the city. The low-cost sensors which make this work possible are designed and built at Makerere university and cost approximately \$250, where high-cost commercial sensors can cost up to \$100,000. The cheapest sensor (Shinyei PPD42NS particulate sensor) that could be found was used as a single sensor and later on the project evolved and The Development Impact Lab at Berkeley (University of California) funded the initial investment of more sensors. Newer designs combine multiple sensors, a solar charging system and the design is improved to handle the hot, dusty and humid conditions in Kampala. A team of software engineers, data scientists and technicians in Kampala and at the University of Sheffield have created the IoT infrastructure and related software architecture to collect and store this data. The next phase of the project will use machine learning techniques to address issues of calibration, optimal sensor placement and improved prediction of air quality levels. Multi-task learning allows the use of many low-cost sensors and minimal high-cost sensors to combine different resolutions and sensor types to improve predictions across Kampala. These strategies will be used going forward in different cities in Uganda as well as across Africa to provide low-cost access to data which can inform policy decisions across the continent.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 109

Applicant details

Submission category: S - Research Datasets and Databases

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Turner, Robert

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

This dataset contains environmental metrics (air quality, temperature) which are important for informing both day-to-day decisions for the general public, and larger scale decisions by policy makers and businesses. Data covering Sheffield (UK) is made available by the University of Sheffield's Urban Flows Observatory (<https://sheffield-portal.urbanflows.ac.uk/uflobin/ufportal>), part of a network of centres around the country. While we have entered this in the "Research Datasets and Databases" category, there are many roles that are involved in bringing it to use. The observatory both deploys its own sensors and collates data from collaborators (e.g. Sheffield City Council). The data is achieved indefinitely using an adaptation of the NetCDF file format and is query-able via an SQL-like interface, which efficiently returns data in a storage system organized by time. This allows researchers to address big questions e.g. around how legislation intended to reduce pollution impacts on health over periods of years. The team are working towards using FAIR data principles and standard schemata / vocabularies with many of the core principles already achieved.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 111

Applicant details

Submission category: G - Software

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Richmond, Paul

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

FLAME GPU (www.flamegpu.com) is a cross-platform general purpose complex system simulation framework, which abstracts the technical requirements of parallel and GPU programming behind a high level API. This allows domain-specific researchers with limited programming skill to implement highly performant agent based simulations that can be executed on HPC. The software underpins important international H2020 research projects, e.g. (PRIMAGE, Strituvad) and is further utilised and developed by a number of PhD students. The software has demonstrated considerable impact and forms the foundation for collaborations on digital twin simulations (with SIEMENS), simulation of transportation networks (funded by DFT T-TRIG) and most recently in supporting RateSetter++ a project with Rail Standards and Safety Board (as well as UKRI Covid-9 rolling funding) looking at simulation approaches to understanding constraints around safe train platform interfaces for pedestrians during social distancing. The software has grown in maturity over the last 12 years from a single student PhD project to a project which has had contributions from ~5 RSEs and ~6 PhD students. It is currently maintained by the RSE Sheffield group and is an exemplar of software best practice utilising agile development methodologies and use of GitHub processes for team contributions, continuous integration and an extensive test suite, accessible interfaces to lower level languages (through Python), performance optimisation, extensive documentation and a well developed user guide with example models. The research papers which describe novel aspects/uses of FLAME GPU have received 478 citations. A recent talk at the GPU technology conference received 235 views and the software has run tutorials and the ALife conference for the last 3 consecutive years.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 118

Applicant details

Submission category: G - Software

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Hodgkinson, Mark

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

ATLAS is one of four experiments, which study proton-proton collisions, at the Large Hadron Collider at CERN in Switzerland. The ATLAS collaboration consists of 3000 scientists who have jointly published 63 papers with the dataset recorded between 2015 and 2018 (known as “Run 2”). These papers include many measurements of the properties of the newly discovered Higgs Boson particle (the discovery of which led to the 2012 Nobel Prize for the theorists who predicted its existence). For this to be possible the raw data from the ATLAS experiment has to be processed to produce a data format which scientists can analyse. This step is run once to produce that data format, which contains for example the measured energy and directions of the different particles produced in the proton-proton collisions. I co-lead currently, and did so throughout Run 2, the ATLAS Reconstruction Integration Group, a team of around 30 research software engineers at institutes worldwide, to provide the software used in the aforementioned workflow. Within this group teams develop pattern recognition software to group signals in the particle detectors in such a way that they can be unambiguously assigned to one particle (for example this could be an electron). We then run a sequence of these algorithms, written in c++, integrated together, known as the “reconstruction”, to produce the final data format. We make use of industry standard tools such as Jira to track software bugs and track work on new features, as well as code reviews of all new contributions and an extensive suite of software tests on said contributions. These algorithms are a subset of the software contained in the ATLAS “athena” software (<https://zenodo.org/record/3933810>). This is not publishable work in a journal, but this reconstruction software is a critical ingredient that underpins the 63 papers published with the Run 2 dataset.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 128

Applicant details

Submission category: G - Software

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Summers, John

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Software comes in many forms. Since computing has been enabled by such great deals of miniaturization, the computers we have today are the best we have ever had. Even though these statements are platitudes, they are obviously true. Not all software, however is built according to effective rules of design. In operations environment it is easy to find examples of software that is just haphazardly patched together with foxhole prayers. Many of us have made implementations by the seat of our pants. The great hope is that eventually we devote more time to building software to stand the test of time. It might be a bit unrealistic to expect beautiful innovation in operations environments. However innovation in such environments is essential to human existence. While the implementation that is the subject of this submission hasn't necessarily not been done before, the hope is that it serves a specific purpose in text processing contexts and is well designed. Something small is typically easier to build. In the case of the Summers' Number Stemmer we are talking about a simple form of artificial intelligence that does not in any way other than electricity rely upon the laws of probability to do what it does. Given a positive integer, this number stemmer adds suffixes commonly associated with ordinal values: first, second, third, fourth, fifth ... and so on until the numbers become so large they cannot be supported. Knowing how to do this is important. Knowing when to do it is another matter. When depends upon various forms of neural nets. How however is not dependent on chance. See <http://stopthemoacks.com/sns.txt> for an implementation of the Summers' Number Stemmer in Java.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 129

Applicant details

Submission category: G - Software

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Schuppert, Victoria

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

I would like to nominate Vertigo Ventures (VV), in particular VV Impact Tracker. Brunel University London uses VV-Impact Tracker to capture, measure and report the social, economic, and environmental impact of academic staff. As a project management tool, the Tracker has been invaluable for our 60 case studies across all 4 main panels and fundamentally helped us cultivate our commitment to supporting world-class research and impact, including impact that is not captured by the REF. The Tracker helped us catch all impact projects, and not solely those we submitted to the REF, and ensured no one got left behind regardless of 'REF-eligibility' or lack thereof. VV provides a range of benefits of which the almost 2,500 indicators to measure impact is a fundamental part. Those indicators were particular useful when it came to brainstorming for impact case studies which still needed to be developed or, in some cases, 'upgraded' to aim for a higher score. This was the case across disciplines, Business and Management Studies and Anthropology and Development Studies only being 2 examples out of several. The software played a key role in Brunel's management of the REF impact case studies, not least because it also served as a kind of 'Dropbox' which allowed us to store all corroborating evidence securely until it was ready to be uploaded to the REF submission system. Like certain research outputs tend to get overlooked (perhaps most commonly the 'non-publication based' outputs, i.e. the practice-based outputs), so does the software behind the people without which any REF preparation would be made much, much harder. This is why, staying in line with recognising 'all people, all research and all categories', the software behind all of it deserves a celebration of its own. For our actual human contact at VV, please get in touch with Andy.Styles@vertigoventures.com.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 140

Applicant details

Submission category: G - Software

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Sena, Emily

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Systematic review (SR) and meta-analysis are powerful approaches which summarise and appraise evidence related to specific research questions and highlight needs for further research and research improvement. Our research has highlighted that such insights are pivotal for successfully building on preclinical research. However, due to the high volume and velocity of publication, conducting SRs is time-consuming and resource-intensive. We therefore developed the Systematic Review Facility (SyRF: <http://syrf.org.uk/>; doi: 10.1136/bmj-2020-100103): a freely available online platform designed specifically for the scale and complexity of preclinical SRs. Through ensuring efficient, robust and reproducible data and process management, SyRF enables researchers to collaborate easily, manage projects efficiently, screen and annotate studies and extract outcome data. It is adaptable to a wide range of research questions and study designs. For instance, SyRF facilitates crowd-sourcing, making large-scale reviews feasible; and can be used to develop, validate and leverage automation tools to expedite SRs. Training resources and guidance are provided on the platform to support widespread uptake. Initially funded by the NC3Rs in 2013, SyRF now has 1683 registered users across 76 countries, working on 807 projects, many of which would not have been feasible without the SyRF platform. Insights from these projects have contributed to, for example: new recommendations to enhance the value of preclinical pain research (doi: 10.1097/j.pain.0000000000002269), the development of the updated ARRIVE guidelines (doi: 10.1371/journal.pbio.3000410), a SR of guidelines for internal validity in preclinical biomedical experiments (doi: 10.1136/bmj-2019-100046); used to inform laboratory studies in an EU-funded programme with major industry partners (<https://quality-preclinical-data.eu/>) and to inform a training course for researchers to maximise the impact of their research by increasing study validity (launching June 2021). SyRF has also enabled us to demonstrate the feasibility of living overviews, providing an up-to-date summary of annotated primary studies related to COVID-19 (<https://camarades.shinyapps.io/COVID-19-SOLES/>).

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 148

Applicant details

Submission category: P - Devices and Products

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Hopkins, Jenna

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

A developmental psychologist wanted to research if babies can be trained to reach for a tactile stimulation on their body. To implement tactile stimulation the psychologist wanted to use a tiny silent buzzer attached to the baby's head. Initially the researcher tried a wired buzzer. However, securing the buzzer to the baby's head was problematic as when the baby moved the buzzer either came off or the wire was pulled out by the baby leading to health hazard. To overcome this a new approach was developed to design a comfy-cap using remote control (Wi-Fi or Bluetooth) technology. The brief was to create a manually controllable vibrotactor device to be used on an infant's head. The device needed to be lightweight and as unnoticeable to the infant as possible and incorporated into a baby's hat. The initial specification was to have a battery pack held by the mother whilst holding their child. However, after discussing what the ideal device for this research would be, we delivered beyond the initial expectations by using lightweight batteries incorporated within the hat. The baby could wear the cap without distraction from wires while the components in the cap are controlled remotely. This expanded the research capabilities by enabling the use of the device on a baby whilst they could move around freely. Implementing this design required suitable hardware including light weight Arduino Bluno microcontroller, high frequency coin/button type vibrator, coin cells battery to power the microcontroller, and suitable software to control the microcontroller remotely. Significant difficulties which we resolved included altering the level of vibration that the device emitted to ensure it was not too strong, addressing a power drain issue with the LED component, and carefully calibrating the device so that the vibration level was consistent when the LED was on and off.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 149

Applicant details

Submission category: S - Research Datasets and Databases

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Hopkins, Jenna

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Geographical location information of study subjects plays a significant role in several areas of research within our Department of Psychology at the University of Essex. Lower Layer Super Output Areas (LSOA) provide a hierarchy of geographic areas which are used in statistical analysis to evaluate locational patterns and variations. Translating postcodes into their corresponding LSOA provides challenges due to the large quantity of data involved, as well as issues arising when there are errors in data provided for study subjects. For the benefit of multiple research teams, a task was undertaken to develop a database system that could be connected to Qualtrics (a survey platform) which would validate postcode data being entered and identify the corresponding LSOA areas. Because of the large file size, in order to use the department's Webmate service the data needed to be split up and imported in batches of smaller datasets. So, subsets of data were created and imported successfully ready to be connected for use. To connect to the database and return the codes to Qualtrics, a PHP script was created. It validates and sanitises the postcode inputs, then searches the data for the corresponding LSOA and returns it. This gives an easy path for staff to get the data as one xml query in the Qualtrics javascript will be enough. As this is now complete any member of the Department can connect to the database to get the participants' LSOA and see their broad statistical data.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 150

Applicant details

Submission category: S - Research Datasets and Databases

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Konovalov, Alexander

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Nominating ATLAS of Finite Group Representations (<http://brauer.maths.qmul.ac.uk/Atlas/v3/>), a database prepared by Robert Wilson, Peter Walsh, Jonathan Tripp, Ibrahim Suleiman, Richard Parker, Simon Norton, Simon Nickerson, Steve Linton, John Bray, and Rachel Abbott, and widely used in group theory (see e.g. citations at <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=MQ3Kp8wAAAAJ&hl=en>). It is accessible in GAP (an open source system for computational discrete algebra) via its package AtlasRep(<https://www.gap-system.org/Packages/atlasrep.html>) by Robert A. Wilson, Richard A. Parker, Simon Nickerson, John N. Bray, Thomas Breuer. Recently there's been an interest in reproducibility of these results (see <https://arxiv.org/abs/1603.08650>).

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 158

Applicant details

Submission category: P - Devices and Products

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Rogerson, Cordelia

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

The British Library's Risk Assessment Matrix (RAM) provides an effective, efficient method to assess the impact and likelihood of conservation risks to collection materials. It also helps to identify the most appropriate risk mitigations. It has been used successfully in a range of conservation projects, involving individual items and large collections. The RAM allows large quantities of information to be processed clearly and concisely. A colour-coded traffic light system means assessments are easily comprehended by non-specialists. Risks are assessed using two criteria—impact and likelihood—rated on a scale of 1-5. Once risks are identified, mitigations can be considered and risks re-evaluated. It can be easily updated if new information emerges. The RAM has been successfully used on numerous projects since 2013. It was used to: maintain a risk assessment during a loan of the Lindisfarne Gospels to Durham; recommend relocating extensive acetate microfilm collections to the British Film Institute; and, inform pest management policies in a library-wide assessment. For an exhibition marking the 800th anniversary of the Magna Carta, the RAM enabled decisions about reframing the iconic documents. This took into account information from conservators, imaging scientists, curators, and external stakeholders including the media and researchers. Criteria included: minimal intervention, retreatment possibilities, readability for researchers, and public accessibility. Ultimately, a low-tech solution was identified, minimising risks and meeting all stakeholders' criteria. The matrix—an efficient but comprehensive assessment tool—makes it possible to advocate for the best outcomes for objects. It facilitates structured, neutral discussions between various stakeholders. Moreover, it can be demonstrated that high-profile objects do not necessarily require expensive/high-tech solutions. Lessons learned from using the RAM have been disseminated widely, including blogposts on the BL Collections Care website, which has a large, international audience. We have also published in high-profile journals and conferences, including *Restaurator* and *ICON*.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A

Entry: 160

Applicant details

Submission category: S - Research Datasets and Databases

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Lovering, Ruth

Organisation/University: N/A

Nominating other (name): N/A, N/A

Nominating other (organisation): N/A

Description of submission

Summary

Gene Ontology (GO) is a gold-standard universal resource used globally for analysing and interpreting of high-throughput proteomic, transcriptomic and genomic datasets. GO is developed and curated by several different groups, based at scientific institutions around the world, working together under the auspices of the GO Consortium. The GO Consortium supplies two freely available datasets which provide: 44,000 ontology terms to describe biological roles and cellular locations. 940 million associations of the ontology terms with gene products across 1.2 million species. These associations are known as gene annotations and they capture biological functional knowledge by associating gene products with GO terms. 6.2 million of these gene annotations have been supplied by biocurators who have reviewed the information published in 164,034 scientific articles – this is called manual annotation. 588,740 of these manual gene annotations describe nearly 30,000 human genes. I lead the UCL functional gene annotation group and to date we have curated 10,073 genes and supplied over 74,064 annotations through the review of 7,625 articles. Almost 70% (50,637) of these annotations describe 5,523 human genes, thus we have provided over 8% of all human GO gene annotations. In addition, we are the only group in the world focused on the GO annotation of human microRNAs. Consequently, all of the 7,781 GO annotations associated with human microRNAs are attributed to a UCL source. During our work we have also contributed to the development and revision of over 3,100 ontology terms, with many describing neurological and cardiovascular areas of biology. The value of the GO Consortium resources is demonstrated by over 29,000 citations of the first publication describing GO (Ashburner et al., 2000). Thus, our biocuration effort is of value to biomedical research communities globally by rendering GO more suitable for analysis of high-throughput datasets.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

N/A

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

N/A

Further details

ORCID: N/A

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: N/A

Funding acknowledgements: N/A